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D5.1. CDSMP Implementation plan

WP5: Implementation of the Intervention

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¹ PU = Public

CDSMP IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

CDSMP: Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme

CHUM: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Montpellier

CSO: Civil Society Organizations

CSPA: Consejería de Salud del Principado de Asturias

D: Deliverable

Dn.n: Deliverable number

EC: European Commission

EGO: Ente Galliera Ospedali

EMC: Erasmus Medical Center

GA: Grant Agreement

HCS: Health Care Services

THTA: Talking Health, Taking Action

ID: Identification number

ICPC: International Classification of Primary Care

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

Mn: Month (number)

MPI: Multidimensional Pronostic Index

NGO: Non-Governmental Organization

NHS: National Health Service

No: Number

PACAS: Paciente Activo Asturias

PC: Project coordinator

QISMET: Quality Institute for Self-Management Education & Training

UK: United Kingdom

WP: Work Package

SECTION 1: EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1. The project EFFICHRONIC.

Chronic diseases can be prevented by reducing risk factors related to high blood pressure, consumption of tobacco and/or alcohol, hyperglycemia, stress or obesity among other factors. These risk factors are mostly linked to unhealthy lifestyles and can be successfully modified by using appropriate health practices. In line with this, a relevant number of programmes have shown evidence on their positive impact on chronic conditions, secondary prevention and management, but there are limited data on their efficiency and cost-benefit. This lack of data typically reduces the policy engagement and support to these programmes and prevents health systems from being more sustainable and efficient. On the other hand, socio-economic factors are known to be extremely important health determinants. This project goes beyond the current state of the art on chronic disease management by carrying out an analysis of cost-efficiency data of chronic disease secondary prevention and management evidenced-based programmes through the integration of social determinants of health.

The project EFFICHRONIC aims to provide evidence on the positive return of investment and cost-efficiency of the application of the Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme (CDSMP) in 5 different European countries (France, Italy, The Netherlands, Spain and UK) with a particular focus on the health-related, medical, social, cultural and economic factors that are linked with a higher burden of chronic disorders in Europe.

1.2. Purpose, objectives and scope.

The two **main objectives** of this deliverable are the following:

1. Present the compilation of data and review of all actions carried out to respond to the objectives of WP 5 “Implementation of the intervention” covering the programme implementation period of the project EFFICHRONIC, from M6 to M34.
2. Analyze and evaluate the process of recruitment and the final results in the five European pilot sites where the CDSMP was implemented in vulnerable population, from a quantitative and a qualitative perspective.

The **specific objectives** of this deliverable derive from the tasks described in WP5 and are defined as follows:

1. Sample recruitment in the 5 countries according to the designed strategies.
2. Preparation of the intervention programme.
3. Implementation of the CDSMP.
4. Qualitative evaluation of the recruitment strategies.

The **scope** of this report is on describing the process of engaging, stratifying and quantifying the target population and pave the room to the development of policy recommendations. This report is public and provides also useful information for people involved in health promotion and prevention activities in sociocultural disadvantaged populations with chronic conditions and / or caregivers.

This deliverable is built on previous reports prepared by the members of the consortium, and is linked to other work packages and already submitted deliverables. More specifically, there is a strong link with WP4 (Stratification: and vulnerability multidimensional analysis), Task 4.4 (Recruiting and engagement strategies design), and the corresponding deliverable (D4.2 Ethics, methodologies and standards). It is also based on WP2 (Dissemination and Communication strategy) including its deliverables D2.1 Communication Resources, D2.2 Dissemination and Communication activities report and D2.3 Dissemination and Communication evaluation report.

1.3. Methodology.

The results obtained after the implementation of the CDSMP in the five pilots in four dimensions are summarized:

1. Sample recruitment in the 5 countries according to the designed strategies.

Thanks to the mixture of recruitment strategies and the high number of involved entities, more than **2951 participants** distributed over the five countries have been **successfully engaged** in the CDSMP programme during the 18 months of the recruitment phase.

2. Preparation of the intervention programme.

All pilot sites trained the necessary number (32) of leaders to conduct the workshops in the community, and even exceed the objective: more than **234 leaders were trained**. They also adapted the programme material to be able to implement the intervention in their territory. The dissemination activities and recruitment strategies contributed to the successful preparation of the programme.

3. Implementation of the CDSMP.

People with chronic conditions and caregivers from the following vulnerable groups attended the programme: ethnic minorities, immigrants, refugees, elderly people living alone or in institutions, people with few economic resources or living in therapeutic communities, inmates, and members of many associations. In total, 2951 people started training and **2317 finished** four out of six sessions, meaning a participant loss of 21%.

4. Qualitative evaluation of the recruitment strategies:

it provides another insight into the implementation, and takes into account the input from human and logistic factors of the coordinators of the recruitment. As facilitating elements for recruitment, key aspects have been

identified: working closely and very coordinated with all the agents involved, making the project widely known, working with stakeholders with a broad expertise, solidity and social recognition which guarantee credibility and leadership, and the rural environment as a factor favoring recruitment strategies for vulnerable populations.

1.4. Conclusions

After the analysis of the results of the project considering both the quantitative results and the qualitative approach, the main conclusions are:

1. **Necessity of extra time in the implementation phase.** The foreseen project lifetime was not sufficient to implement a CDSMP programme in vulnerable populations in five countries, and reach a sample size of 2000 people. A project extension of 6 months was needed to successfully accomplish the objectives. The main reasons for deviation were that vulnerable population are harder to reach than general population, and three out of five pilot sites started from scratch.
2. **Effective mitigation actions were needed.** The different starting points from the partners have been a rich source of learning. Strengths and weaknesses of the recruitment strategies were rapidly identified and all study sites have been able to implement effective mitigation actions to reach the objectives.
3. **Different starting situations and unforeseen obstacles resulted in differences in results at different pilot sites.** The different organizational structures of the EFFICHRONIC partners required them to adapt the theoretical framework to their specific reality, adding a complementary dimension to the project.
4. **The strategic coordination of agents with different backgrounds has been a success factor.** Healthcare, social work and community - and at different levels - ministries, city councils and associations were coordinated at the local-regional level to obtain optimum results during the recruitment phase. A great variety of key agents from different sectors in the territories must be engaged in the recruitment process. It has been fundamental that the various strategies were implemented simultaneously and that the process has been coordinated by an effective project management team to optimize the results.

1.5. Recommendations.

For future research projects that involve the implementation of a self-management programme, or any other health promotion programme, a longer period of implementation is recommended (12 months in our case) to be able to:

1. Adapt the programme and its materials to each environment.

2. Prepare the training of the CDSMP Leaders appropriately in advanced so that they can acquire practice and achieve a good learning curve.
3. Map the stakeholders that work with vulnerable populations previously, get to know them, and coordinate them.

Also, carrying out qualitative analysis simultaneously to capture the richness of the processes, the strengths and weaknesses reported by the intermediate agents, as well as the areas for improvement, is recommended.

SECTION 2: PURPOSE, OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

2.1 Purpose.

The purpose of this deliverable is twofold:

1. To describe the carried out actions and strategies designed to achieve the specific objective of WP5: “To implement the program in the 5 regions, including the appropriate measures to involve at least 400 individuals of the stratified / identified populations in each setting (N = 2000)”.
2. To analyze the process and the final results at the five EFFICHRONIC pilot sites where the CDSMP has been implemented in vulnerable European populations.

2.2 Objectives.

To achieve the aims of WP5, four major objectives were identified. From these three correspond to the different tasks of the work package as described in the Grant Agreement, and the fourth adds a qualitative evaluation of the recruitment strategies.

1. **Sample recruitment in the 5 countries according to the designed recruitment strategies.**

According to the fundamentals set in the previous WP and expecting to collect a sample of 2000 individuals (+ additional individuals to reduce the effect of the expected 20% experimental mortality), we aim to target 250.000 persons by physicians, nurses social workers, associations, stakeholders, community oriented actions and other additional dissemination actions (such as via word to mouth, multipliers, social media, etc). The final expected sample should cover 400 individuals from each country with a chronic condition and caregivers but demonstrating self-management of their condition.

2. Preparation of the intervention programme.

The preparation of the programme includes the training of CDSMP monitors in countries without previous programme experience. In deliverable D6.1, the training cascade and philosophy of the programme is described more in detail.

The monitors receive specific training on the Stanford Methodology by certified trainers, in the following areas: empowerment, self-efficacy, positive health and healthy habits. A minimum of 32 monitors per country (160 total), preferably identified among recruited individuals, are trained to conduct the workshops in the community.

3. Implementation of the CDSMP.

To carry out the intervention, it is necessary to define an initial mapping of stakeholders, to identify them, contact them and propose their collaboration for engaging vulnerable populations. As a first step, the Geographical Areas of greatest population vulnerability explained in Deliverable D4.2. Ethics, Methodologies and standards need to be considered.

Contacts and alliances have been made with the relevant stakeholders who are the intermediaries in the access and recruitment of the vulnerable population.

In previous reports, the fundamentals of the CDSMP are explained in detail. The duration of the programme is of 15 hours during 6 weeks (2,5 hours per week). The main contents are: fundamentals of self-management, making action plans, relaxation, cognitive symptom management, problem-solving, painful emotions, fitness and exercise, better breathing, fatigue, healthy diet, communication, medications, making treatment decisions and working with healthcare professionals.

All the Monitors must be previously trained and accredited. They implement the training in pairs in vulnerable population groups previously defined. The workshops are held in the community in pairs in social and geographical areas, until completing a recommended number that ranges between 27 and 40 workshops. Typically, between 10 and 15 people attend each workshop.

4. Qualitative evaluation of the recruitment strategies.

The involvement of all different social actors is particularly important from the perspective of adopting a Responsible Research approach. This approach requires to explore how all these stakeholders interact with each other and these interactions work in order to enhance a model of science based on its acceptability, sustainability and social convenience.

Therefore, the correct identification of the candidates to be recruited to participate in the CDSMP is a highly complex process. This has been included as a key objective in the project, given the fact that it requires collaborative work with a variety of stakeholders at local level as a central step for the recruitment process.

A qualitative analysis of the recruitment process will be performed taking into account the different sociocultural realities and models of health systems. For this, we planned specific interviews with the project leaders who have been responsible for the development of this complex network of relationships with stakeholders. Project leaders have been selected to be interviewed because they have a deep knowledge of how the process has been implemented.

2.3 Scope.

This report aims to analyze the strategies that have been developed throughout the implementation of EFFICHRONIC in order to reach vulnerable population in Europe. The process developed and the conclusions derived from the participation, stratification and quantification of the target population will serve for the future development of policy recommendations. The scope of the obtained results and strengths and weaknesses identified can be considered in other European regions when working with population that are at risk of vulnerability or are difficult to access.

This report also provides useful information for the scientific community who develop their activity on health promotion and prevention in populations with chronic diseases and / or caregivers who suffer from disadvantaged sociocultural conditions. This document will also help local or national organizations, town halls, local corporations, NGOs, patient associations, etc. that are able to undertake actions to improve their citizen's health.

SECTION 3: METHODOLOGY

For a better understanding, it is necessary to highlight that the methodology of the WP5 (Implementation of the Intervention), is executed in three tasks that have been completely described in previous deliverables and are now finished. These tasks are:

Task 1. Recruitment of the sample in the 5 countries according to the strategies designed. The target population of the EFFICHRONIC intervention are vulnerable people with chronic conditions or caregivers. The rationale for choosing this target population and the specific inclusion and exclusion criteria are described in D4.1. “List of clinical and social variables and MPI index,” delivered in May 2018.

The recruitment framework is described in detail in the Deliverable 4.2. “Ethics, methodology and standards” (May 2018) where the different techniques and the strategic approaches used during the recruitment phase have been discussed. In D2.2. “Dissemination and Communication activities report” (November 2019), communication and dissemination activities aimed at recruiting the vulnerable population and involving stakeholders have been compiled and analysed.

Task 2. Preparation of the intervention programme. The actions considered in compliance with the data protection law and the ethical considerations prior to the intervention are discussed in Deliverable 4.2.

Task 3. Implementation of the CDSMP. Partial data of the implementation, up to the date of submission of each document, were reflected in the Periodic Technical Report (submitted in January 2019).

This section details the methods to accomplish the three tasks of WP5: sample recruitment, intervention preparation, and implementation, with the overall goal of achieving full implementation at all the pilot sites. In addition, a qualitative analysis of the recruitment strategies used at the five sites will be carried out.

3.1 Sample recruitment.

Targeting and recruiting populations

The vulnerable target groups were defined and agreed by the entire EFFICHRONIC consortium, and were defined in detail in the sample inclusion criteria to ensure a rigorous quality during intervention. These include persons older than 18 years who meet one of the following conditions:

1. Situation 1: Isolated Caregivers

- Caregiver: a person that takes care of someone with an illness. Caregivers do not necessarily need to have a chronic condition, but they must have a vulnerability condition to be selected for EFFICHRONIC.
- Vulnerability condition: isolation. The criterion of isolation is fulfilled when the participants are:
 - without access or limited access of transport (without private car and without public transport near the place of residence - more than 1 km far away from home),
 - or**
 - digitally isolated: without Wi-Fi or internet.

2. Situation 2: Vulnerable people with a chronic disease

Participants in the programme must have at least one chronic disease and also comply with one of the vulnerability criteria shown below.

- A chronic condition (self-reported or clinically evaluated by medical staff) according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2) is defined as a chronic pathology with code between 70 and 99 with at least six months of evolution.
- Vulnerability conditions:
 - o **Elderly people** (older than 65 years of age) living alone.
 - o **Inmates.**
 - o **Ethnic minorities on a low income.**
 - o **Legal immigrants, refugees and asylum-seekers on a low income.** For the asylum-seekers the domicile must be known for at least 6 months.
 - o **Other vulnerable persons on a low income** even if not included in the previous target groups.

Framework for the recruitment

The methods that were designed for the recruitment of vulnerable people with chronic conditions and caregivers in EFFICHRONIC have been extensively explained in **D4.2: “Ethics, Methodologies and Standards”**, submitted in May 2018. The report describes how the recruitment methodology is built on two dimensions of vulnerability: population parameters on the one hand and individual characteristics on

the other. It provides more details on the project-specific recruitment methods and how they were developed.

The first pillar refers to the **social dimension** of vulnerability, considering societal factors and people's social and economic environment. Areas classified as vulnerable in all regions are likely to harbour a large amount of people eligible for EFFICHRONIC and therefore, recruitment efforts were mainly focussed there. To easily identify these areas, vulnerability maps were elaborated for France, Italy and Spain and the UK, and existing maps were consulted online. The vulnerability maps could not be designed in the Netherlands due to the lack of census data, and local stakeholders were involved in determining the most suitable areas. Please, see section 2.3 of D4.2 for more details.

Evolution of the recruitment and mitigation measures

As the project developed, it became clear that, mostly due to the lack of previous CDSMP experience on the one hand in some countries, and practical obstacles appearing on the way on the other hand, it was rather difficult to reach the initial stipulated sample size if the project was to end in June 2020 as foreseen.

For this reason, at the EFFICHRONIC General Assembly meeting in Rotterdam in May 2019, the possibility to request a project extension was discussed and all partners voted in favour. The motivated report was submitted to the EU Platform on July 29, 2019. The requested extension of 6 months was signed and granted on September 9, 2019.

The two main arguments to ask for this extension were:

1. Ensuring a sample size that allows a statistically significant analysis of the evaluation framework parameters and ensures the cost-effectiveness analysis.
2. Achieving greater homogeneity of the sample population.

The report also includes all partners' planned corrective actions, including a more intensive communication campaign at each pilot site, the planning of further networking with stakeholders and a specific number of additional workshops to be organized during the extension period. Please see Annex 1 "Motivated report for the six-month extension request of EFFICHRONIC" for further details.

3.2 Preparation of the intervention programme

CDSMP Programme

The programme sessions in groups of 12 to 20 participants take place during 6 weeks, with one session of 2,5 hours per week. A basic element of the programme is the peer-to-peer education, implying the 2 leaders are caregivers or have chronic conditions themselves. The most important topics covered during the weekly sessions are: making weekly action plans, problem-solving, decision-making, relaxation, cognitive symptom management, painful emotions, fitness/exercise, better breathing, healthy diet, communication, medications, depression, and working with health care professionals. Most importantly, the programme motivates people to take control of their life and self-manage their disease. More details on the programme philosophy are provided in Section 3.2, CDSMP implementation, of report D6.1 “Evaluation design and plan report” (May 2019).

CDSMP Training

Leaders or monitors who conduct the CDSMP workshops in the community had to be trained before the implementation could start, especially in countries where the CDSMP had not been implemented before and no leader network existed. The monitors needed to receive specific training on the Stanford Methodology by certified trainers. In report D6.1, section 3.2, a detailed description is provided on the CDSMP training cascade and methodology.

Furthermore, an intensive communication and dissemination campaign has been carried out to foster the recruitment of the target populations and increase the visibility of the project at different levels: the public in general, the scientific community and the different groups of target population. The strategies designed for this purpose are extensively described in the reports D2.1 “Communication resources” (August 2017), D2.2 “Dissemination and communication activities Report” (November 2018) and D2.3 “Communication and Dissemination evaluation Report” (May 2019).

SMRC CDSMP license

All EFFICHRONIC pilots offering the SMRC CDSMP programme and organizing the Leadership training must have a specific program license. The CDSMP-specific SMRC license allows the interested organizations to facilitate the programme once the leaders have been trained. Being licensed also involves following the CDSMP Loyalty Manual which ensures that the programme is delivered as designed and follows the quality of the evidence-based programme.

Materials

Different types of material are necessary to carry out the CDSMP workshops. Leaders need the “Leader Manual” and 30 teaching boxes to facilitate the delivery of the programme in the community. End users need a student's dossier, a CD for physical and relaxation exercises (depending on the country) and access to the book "Living a healthy life with chronic conditions". All the materials are in the language of the corresponding country.

Quality Control

T-Trainers, Master Trainers or trained Leaders from the research team (where the previous are not available) in each organization are in charge of ensuring the quality of the training according to the terms of the SMRC license.

In order to ensure the quality standards and the results of this evidence-based programme, which has successfully been running since 30 years, it is necessary to strictly follow the programme's manual and the training cascade. All Leaders facilitating workshops in the community must be audited by T-Trainers, Master Trainers or trained Leaders from the research team.

Data Protection

Workshop participants were informed about data security in the participant's information letter, and informed pre-workshop consents were collected, following the EU Directive 96/46 on data protection.

All EFFICHRONIC participants were clearly informed about the scope of the data collection, the legal basis for the processing of personal data, how long the data is kept, if the data would be transferred to a third party and / or outside the EU, and disclosure of any automated decision making (not applicable in EFFICHRONIC). Users were provided with contact details for data management and were informed of their rights, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council, of April 27, 2016, on the protection of natural persons with respect to the processing of personal data and the free circulation of these data.

At any time, participants were able to exercise their data protection rights. Only the research team and health authorities (if applicable), who have a duty to maintain confidentiality, had/will have access to all data collected from the study. Only information that cannot be identified can be passed on to third parties. In case of transmission of information to other countries, it will be done anonymously with a level of data protection, in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Data will be collected and retained until the study is completed in encrypted form. The person responsible for data custody is responsible for data archiving and processing. At the end of the study, the data will be kept anonymized. EOG will keep all the data referring to the Selfy-MPI, and EMC will store the baseline and follow-up questionnaires of the study.

Key Concepts

To better understand the results of this report, it is convenient to understand the different definitions related to the implementation results of EFFICHRONIC:

- **Number of workshops:** This is the total number of completed workshops (consisting of 6 sessions) that have been conducted at the project sites in the framework of EFFICHRONIC.
- **Engaged people:** Recruited people who actually signed up for the programme and who attended at least one out of six sessions.
- **Number of people who completed the CDSMP:** Participants who completed the programme successfully. These are participants who attended minimum four out of the six sessions of the programme.
- **Number of baseline questionnaires.** Number of filled out baseline questionnaires² from participants who completed the CDSMP properly.
- **Number of selfy-MPI questionnaires.** The selfy-MPI is the instrument used to stratify the study population. Participants fill it out when starting the workshop. Its development and purpose is described in detail report **D4.1 “List of clinical variables and MPI index”**, issued in May 2018.
- **Number of follow-up questionnaires³.** This reflects the number of participants who completed the CDSMP and who filled out both the baseline and follow-up questionnaire. The moment of follow-up is at 6 months post-intervention. This report does not provide the final information as the last follow-up questionnaires will be collected in August 2020, 6 months after the last workshops started.

3.3 Implementation of the CDSMP

The implementation of the CDSMP in EFFICHRONIC has been carried out between M6 to M34.

Recruitment strategies

The starting point for developing the project-specific recruitment methodology was designed based on a detailed bibliographic analysis, and taking into account the individual characteristics of vulnerable people. The main results can be found in the document: "Strategies for identifying and recruiting hard-to-reach populations. Discussion paper" (Annex 2).

² The baseline questionnaires were described in D6.1. Evaluation design and plan report (May 2019)

³ The follow-up questionnaires were described in D6.1. Evaluation design and plan report (May 2019)

The working document was prepared with the aim of encouraging and supporting the discussions of professionals, experts and decision-makers in each National event organized at each EFFICHRONIC pilot site, and developing effective strategies to reach the identified vulnerable individuals and groups. Also, this document is intended to be a guide for reflection, debate and discussion before the start of the workshops of stakeholders organized in the framework of the National event organized in Asturias at the beginning of the Project”.

Therefore, this document has been a work in progress document that was initially provided as a discussion guide for the workshops of stakeholders, and which was later enriched with the contributions and suggestions of the experts. Stakeholders defined their vulnerable target population, successful interventions, and best practices for the implementation phase of EFFICHRONIC.

The structure of Annex II is as follows: the document starts with a brief conceptual discussion on the term "vulnerable" populations and their related terms and reflects the reasons why these populations are difficult to reach for health interventions (with a particular focus on chronic care interventions). Then, a section that identifies and suggests a series of experiences for the sampling, recruitment, and retention of vulnerable people in health interventions based on the literature is presented. The last part contains the tables that identify the most convenient sampling and recruitment strategies to be used by each partner in collaboration with experts and stakeholders,.

The following strategies were initially proposed to detect (map) the stakeholders:

1. Geopolitical recruitment.
2. Recruitment through formal territorial organizations.
3. Transversal recruitment by healthcare professionals.
4. Transversal attraction by social workers and related professionals.
5. Specific recruitment for institutionalized vulnerable people.
6. Uptake by Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO).
7. Recruitment by civil society.

Following the start of the CDSMP workshops and first discussions with relevant stakeholders, an intense dissemination and communication campaign was carried out to promote the recruitment of vulnerable target populations. This strategy is described in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3.

CDSMP Intervention

The implementation of the CDSMP programme has been carried out strictly as described: translated materials, trained leaders, quality control, licensing and all the requirements to comply with data protection regulations and research ethics.

3.4 Qualitative analysis

Target population

As part of the recruitment strategy and patient recruitment for attending the EFFICHRONIC workshops, five people (one per EFFICHRONIC member country) have been appointed to be in charge of contacting relevant stakeholders.

Data Collection

Five interviews of approximately 60 minutes each, with the leaders in the recruitment process of each of the participating countries were previously designed and discussed among experts. The interviews were audio-recorded for later transcription and analysis. Notes were taken during the interview and / or written immediately afterwards if deemed appropriate to increase the interviewee's understanding.

The interviews were carried out through a video call in the interviewee's mother tongue (English, Spanish or Italian).

Topic guideline for the interview

The questions defined to guide the interview are:

- Would you like to start by discussing how the process of recruitment of stakeholders was?
- How were all relevant stakeholders proposed / found for the recruitment work?
 - Whom did you contact?
 - How did it go?
 - or ...
- Which strategies have been most effective in identifying and involving these stakeholders? And the difficulties?
- Which strategies have been most effective in recruiting vulnerable people (patients and caregivers)?
- Based on your experience, or according to what stakeholders have said, have there been difficulties in recruiting users? What could have made it challenging?
- Have the tools and procedures designed to recruit them been useful? What could be improved? What would you change?

- What have you learnt from this experience of collaborating with local stakeholders for the recruitment of vulnerable populations?
- How has your relationship with the stakeholders changed after engaging in this process?
- How would you think you would do the recruitment process again after this experience?
- Would you like to add something about the topic that was not covered in the interview?

After the transcription of the interviews' recordings, a thematic analysis was conducted. This analysis was carried out through a coding and synthesis process. In a first reading, the codes are attributed to small parts of the text (a code is one or more words that represent what is said in the text that is being analysed). Then, similar codes were grouped into more overarching themes that continue to reflect the original meaning identified in the texts, but that at the same time can represent a more abstract concept and, therefore, can be transferable to other contexts. The NVivo software was used for the analysis.

Ethical considerations

The informed consent of the project leaders has been requested previous execution of the semi-structured interview technique.

This study obtained the approval of the Ethics Committee for Research with Medicines of the Principality of Asturias (nº 118/19). See in Annex 3.

SECTION 4: RESULTS

This deliverable presents the implementation results obtained up to M34 and focuses on the outcomes of the task 5.1 (Sample recruitment), tasks 5.2 (Preparation of the Intervention) and 5.3 (Implementation of the CDSMP). The implementation of the programme began in July 2018 (M14) and finished in March 2020 (M34).

This deliverable presents the implementation results of WP5, obtained up to M34, and focuses on the results of task 5.1 (Sample recruitment), tasks 5.2 (Preparation of the intervention) and 5.3 (Implementation of the CDSMP). This last task 5.3, including the implementation of the programme and the elaboration of the deliverable, started in July 2018 (M14) and ended in March 2020 (M34).

4.1 Sample recruitment

Targeting and recruiting populations

The number of engaged participants had been previously set at 2000 participants. A total number of **2951 vulnerable people has enrolled the CDSMP programme** at the different pilot sites during the execution of EFFICHRONIC. A significantly higher number of participants than that expected have participated in the programme. Table 1 shows the distribution of participants per country and the total number.

Table 1. EFFICHRONIC: Sample recruitment.

	Spain	France	UK	NL	Italy	EFFICHRONIC
Engaged participants	1131	231	577	612	400	2951

The various vulnerable groups already described in section 3.1 have been engaged in the programme. The analysis of the distribution of the sample by country, and the description of the sample and its distribution according to the different vulnerability groups, will be included in the corresponding deliverable of WP6 "Assessment and data analysis".

Nevertheless, a first **qualitative approach** was performed and it can be concluded that, all sites targeted people with low-income but also immigrants, isolated caregivers, older persons living alone or in institutions, roman communities and prisoners. In Italy, there was a stronger emphasis on seniors. In France, Spain and Italy, rural communities were reached with relative success in their engagement at medium-term (so, during the intervention) depending on the material circumstances of the persons involved (e.g., the availability of transport). In Spain, recruitment of institutionalized people, such as in the central prison and therapeutic communities, have been of special interest.

In general, all targeted vulnerable groups for the project were reached in a successful and homogeneous way at all sites.

4.2 Preparation of the intervention

As already developed in D6.1, the first results are related to the process of preparing the material for the intervention and conducting the CDSMP Leaders training. The training materials for Leaders and participants were prepared in the five languages of the EFFICHRONIC consortium: English, French, Italian, Spanish and Dutch. In Spain, the UK and Italy, no extra work was necessary for EFFICHRONIC as the CDSMP programme was already being implemented before the start of the project and available in

each of the corresponding languages. However, In France, all the educational material for Leaders and participants needed to be adapted from the Canadian French version and in the Netherlands the material had to be translated to Dutch. Subsequently, all translations and adaptations were approved by the SMRC.

The second results of the preparation phase refer to the training of Leaders. In the project proposal it was calculated that a minimum of 32 leaders needed to be trained per country, to allow reaching the required sample size of 2.000. The objective was already reached in May 2019 as described in section 4.2 Implementation results of the report D6.1 “Evaluation design and report”.

Nevertheless, due to a higher than expected drop-out rate of trained Leaders at some sites, and/or to increase the availability of the programme in more cities or regions, additional trainings were organised in France, The Netherlands and Spain. The final number of trained leaders even exceeded the necessary number, reaching more than 234 instructed Leaders (see table 2).

In France a new leaders training session was done in August – September 2019, providing 12 additional leaders: 4 for Toulouse, 2 for Perpignan, 3 for Nimes and 3 for Montpellier, allowing the inclusion of 2 more departments (Haute-Garonne and Pyrénées-Orientales). The final number of trained Leaders in France is of 44 CDSMP leaders.

In the Netherlands, the drop-out of Leaders was mitigated by organizing training for about 20 extra Leaders during the summer of 2019, bringing a total number of 52 trained facilitators.

In Asturias, EFFICHRONIC is embedded in the Active Patient Programme (Paciente Activo Asturias) which started in 2015 and will continue to expand once EFFICHRONIC finishes. For this reason, leader trainings are organized on an almost continuous basis allowing the training of a wider profile of Leaders, including more patients and caregivers every time, and distributed over the territory of the region. In June 2019, 13 Leaders were trained in Oviedo and in January 2020 an extra 16 were instructed in Avilés, reaching a total of 70 by the end of the EFFICHRONIC implementation period.

Table 2. Number of trained CDSMP leaders for EFFICHRONIC

Country	May 2019	March 2020	Total
Spain	41	29	70
France	32	12	44
UK	Network previously available		32+
The Netherlands	32	20	52
Italy	36	36	36
EFFICHRONIC			234+

Regarding the licence required to deliver the CDSMP, QISMET and CSPA already had a license. CHUM, EMC and EOG acquired the license that was managed by Vively. Vively is a representative of the Self-Management Resource Center in Europe that is part of the project's External Advisory Board. Vively negotiated for all partners the specific fees associated with the training needs of EFFICHRONIC.

Regarding the quality control of the workshops, i.e., the audit necessary to make sure that the methodology of the CDSMP is preserved in terms of accuracy and fidelity to the teaching method, we followed these steps:

- In France, the team has 3 Master Trainers that were trained in Asturias in March 2018. These are the ones that perform the quality control and carry out the audits according to the criteria established in the “Self-Management Resource Center FIDELITY MANUAL 2019” (<https://www.selfmanagementresource.com/resources/frequently-used-tools/>).
- In the UK, QISMET develops quality standards and manages certification processes for a range of self-management education and training services including the CDSMP. This ensures the accomplishment of the quality standards of all the workshops delivered in this country.
- In Netherlands, a research team collaborator, trained as a Master Trainer at Stanford, has carried out the relevant audits.
- In Italy, the coordinator of the entire recruiting and training circuit, with more experience in the development of the workshops, was in charge of quality control detailed in the Fidelity Manual.
- In Spain, the team has two T-Trainers and 14 Master Trainers, who have worked to ensure the audit of all the workshops delivered.

4.3 Implementation of the CDSMP

Firstly, the recruitment strategies that have been carried out are described. Then, the results derived from the intervention of the CDSMP across the different countries are presented and analysed.

Recruitment strategies

EFFICHRONIC specifically shows that reaching out to vulnerable populations requires stepping beyond the formal boundaries of conventional services, and this entails intersectoral alliances among a wide range of actors, all working together towards the same goal. The process is carried out simultaneously at all European study sites, adapting it to the socio-economic context, the health system and cultural singularities of each country. The development of EFFICHRONIC's recruitment approach is unfolded in three consecutive steps, combining population-based and individual recruitment strategies.

Firstly, vulnerability maps were developed to detect areas with higher vulnerability, to prioritize the intervention there. The areas were identified using specific deprivation indices, employing different methodologies. The maps are based on Population Census data in Spain (the MEDEA index and an ad hoc rural index), France (the FDep index) and Italy (the Crevari and Caranci indices). In the United Kingdom, the national Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) produces an overall relative measure of deprivation and was consulted online. In the Netherlands, the established register-based census does not allow constructing deprivation indexes and the most vulnerable areas at this study site were identified by stakeholders working in the community.

Secondly, alliances were created with actors from different institutions and organizations, such as loco-regional public authorities, professionals from healthcare and social services and civil society representatives. The starting point to create these local networks of stakeholders was a national workshop with the aim, on the one hand, to define the local inclusion and exclusion criteria and on the other, to elaborate a preliminary recruitment strategy and detect its barriers.

The final step of the process consists in identifying end-users and engaging them to participate in the CDSMP workshops, mainly in the areas with high vulnerability scores and under the impulse of the acknowledged stakeholders.

The focus of this section of the deliverable is on the two final steps of the recruitment process: the establishment of a cross-sectoral network of stakeholders and the identification and recruitment of the target population. This work does not pretend to be an exhaustive description of all used methods, but it aims to provide a general idea of how different sectors work together with the same purpose.

To reach the vulnerable target population for EFFICHRONIC, alliances with loco-regional authorities, health services, social care organizations and civil society representatives were generated across the EFFICHRONIC sites. The particular geographical, institutional and administrative characteristics in each territory, however, determine the specific strategy used. Despite the many differences between them, all project partners have something in common: they are obliged to step out of the comfort zone of their usual work environment to achieve such collaborations. Furthermore, and to fully profit from the various approaches, stakeholders from the same region work together and coordinate their actions.

An overriding and complementary strategy directed to stakeholders on the one hand, and the general public and end-users on the other, is the project communication and dissemination campaign using a wide range of media channels: online and printed newspapers and magazines, radio, television, social networks, and also flyers and posters. A solid media campaign is essential to share the project's findings with both the general public and the scientific community. It also allows reaching people who are not attracted by any of the below-described strategies, adapting the messages and material to the specific background of the targeted group.

4.3.1 Institutional alliances

Alliances with different types of regional, municipal and lower-level authorities were created in all involved areas (Table 3). In Asturias for example, a direct link was established between the Public Health Department and the Regional Ministry of Social Services. Also, in the French Occitane region, the Regional Health Authority was contacted to establish a network in the (semi-) rural areas and the Public Health Authority in Wales was likewise involved to identify local programme providers working with vulnerable people. Furthermore, the workshops are continuously being implemented at the Asturian prison because the facility management considers the intervention very useful for the inmate population.

At the local level, the EFFICHRONIC partners actively sought support from city councils contacting mayors and councillors. The objective of creating these alliances was threefold: to announce the project at the municipalities, to mobilize resources for participant transport and caregivers replacement and to help the city council staff with the different organizational aspects of the programme. As an example, the Italian EFFICHRONIC team engaged with the municipality of Genoa and several city council employees assisted in the programme to increase their knowledge on the intervention. In Rotterdam, the municipality was involved from the start and identified and contacted interesting stakeholders. Also, in a remote rural area of Asturias, the coalition of mayors of different villages facilitated the recruitment of participants in what is a very disperse territory.

Table 3. Institutional alliances in EFFICHRONIC

Partner	Stakeholder
Asturias – Spain <i>SESPA/CSPA/FICYT</i>	Regional Ministry of Health of Asturias 'CSPA' Regional Ministry of Social Services of Asturias The Regional Prison of Asturias Board of mayors of the Oscos region Health and Social Care coordination teams in Langreo, Avilés and Gijón
Montpellier – France <i>CHUM</i>	Regional Health Authority of Occitanie
United Kingdom <i>QISMET</i>	Public Health Wales
Rotterdam the Netherlands <i>EMC</i>	Municipality of Rotterdam Municipality of Utrecht
Genoa – Italy <i>EOG</i>	Municipality of Genoa

4.3.2 Collaborations with healthcare organizations

The involvement in the project of the different national health systems is a logical measure not only because four of the five partners work in a healthcare-based institution, but also because subgroups of the target population are in regular contact with many kinds of health workers. This group of professionals has an important influence on patients and they are key figures for recruitment. Community health services, such as primary care centres, clinics and retirement facilities, were prioritized. The Dutch, Italian and French EFFICHRONIC study sites are based at a university or regional hospital, and much of their recruitment efforts focus on sensitizing in-house health care professionals.

An innovative move for recruitment in the project is the involvement of General Councils of professionals, such as doctors or pharmacists. By establishing alliances with these organizations, recruitment is organized through their affiliates. In France, the regional and departmental General Medical Council is involved and in Italy, the EFFICHRONIC team is collaborating with the National Hospital Association. In Asturias, the regional Council of Community Pharmacists is implicated because its network also reaches the most remote areas. Each pharmacist, reference person in the community, can recruit participants who live geographically or socially isolated and who do not interact with other regional agents. This strategic line contributes to focus on recruitment in the immediate environment of the target population.

In places where health and social care coordination teams exist, alliances with them were actively established. For example, in Asturias Health and Social Care Coordination Teams aim to improve coordinative actions between both sectors and organize integrated care activities. The structures are either regulated by law or less formal, such as the Health Councils or Municipal Health Schools. Working with them is key to success in the strategic planning of Citizen Participation projects as they have a high impact in the territory. Table 4 resumes the alliances with healthcare organizations in all participating countries.

Table 4. Healthcare organizations participating in EFFICHRONIC

Partner	Stakeholder
Asturias – Spain <i>SESPA/CSPA/FICYT</i>	Health Service of the Principality of Asturias ‘SESPA’ Central University Hospital of Asturias & all local hospitals Community Health Centers of all areas General Council of Community Pharmacists
Montpellier – France <i>CHUM</i>	Different departments within the collaborating hospital CHUM Centre Hospitalier Clermont-l’Hérault General Council of Medical Doctors of Occitanie and departments Regional Association of private practitioners Health Commission of ‘Pays Cœur d’Hérault’ Centre De Santé Filiéris ‘MAIA’ network for integrated care
United Kingdom <i>QISMET</i>	‘Talking Health, Taking action’ (THTA) National Health Service England ‘Talking Therapies’ (NHS organization in East London)
Rotterdam the Netherlands <i>EMC</i>	Different departments within the collaborating hospital EMC Health Center ‘Zonboog’
Genoa – Italy <i>EOG</i>	National Health Service (ASL) Different departments within the collaborating hospital EOG General Council of Medical Doctors, Nurses and Psychologists National Hospital Association

4.3.3 Involving social services and related entities

The creation of coalitions with community-based social care organizations turned out to be a very important strategy in the project (Table 5). Social workers often work with the most deprived of society, who are usually unreachable by other services. These professionals are generally well-known by their clients and in their community working environment. As such, they have the perfect profile to coordinate the intervention in the territory because of their strategic vision, their expert know-how and reference role.

Because it is such a valuable strategy, all partners organize recruitment through Non-Governmental Organizations working with vulnerable people. These organizations usually have a wide network of volunteers and professionals who have a big impact on the target population. Some of the collaborating NGO's are part of the project External Advisory Board due to their important counselling role. The NGO's, acting as intermediaries, contact and recruit participants among immigrants, refugees, ethnic minorities and people having difficulties to make ends meet.

In the UK, the project benefits from a large existing network of CDSMP-licensed organizations, and of special interest are the ones working with vulnerable populations. In some areas, the National Health Service is involved whilst in others, NGO's or patient associations organize the programme. The type and focus of these organizations depend mostly on the loco-regional circumstances and the kind of target population they serve, such as ethnic minorities or economically deprived groups.

A special effort was made to connect with organizations that allow participant recruitment at (semi)-closed institutions, where people suffer important isolation and deprivation. In Italy for instance, recruitment was sought at the residential long-term care facility linked to the partners' geriatric hospital while in Asturias, active collaborations were established with the regional prison, several nursing homes and also, therapeutic communities. In France, workshops were delivered in a regional Rehabilitation Care facility.

Table 5. Implied social work entities and related services in EFFICHRONIC

Partner	Stakeholder
Asturias – Spain <i>SESPA/CSPA/FICYT</i>	Local social services over the territory Social workers from healthcare institutions NGOs: Red Cross, Cáritas, ACCEM, ONCE Helpline 'El teléfono de la Esperanza' Social centers for the elderly (Pola de Laviana, Gijón, La Felguera) Nursing homes, e.g. Montepío Therapeutic community 'La Santina'
Montpellier – France <i>CHUM</i>	NGOs: ATD Quart monde, Restos du cœur Social workers at the CHUM Social workers at the Municipal centres for social action
United Kingdom <i>QISMET</i>	'BME United' Birmingham 'Chest, Heart and Stroke' Northern Ireland 'Citizens Advice' South Derbyshire 'Action Heart' West Midlands
Rotterdam the Netherlands <i>EMC</i>	DOCK: foundation working with vulnerable groups Humanitas Foundation
Genoa – Italy <i>EOG</i>	General Council of Social workers 'CELIVO' Association Regional Education Institute

4.3.4 Engagement from Civil Society

Many different groups of citizens, such as Roma people, neighbours, patients sharing the same condition, elderly people or women, participate actively in associations with which the EFFICHRONIC partners sought alliances to recruit among their members. These organizations usually offer very specific resources and are highly appreciated by their associates, ensuring high fidelity with the CDSMP. It needs to be underlined that, when working with culturally different and inaccessible populations, (e.g. ethnic minorities) the involvement of sociocultural mediators is fundamental to assure effective recruitment.

Examples of implicated patient associations in Spain are organizations for spinal injuries, visual impairment or hearing loss and in France, the National Association for patients with muscle and neuromuscular genetic disorders is co-operating in three cities. In the Netherlands, we worked with social welfare organizations, which are municipally funded organizations that work at a very local level (in each of the 30 neighbourhoods of Rotterdam) to support vulnerable citizens (for example, teenage mothers, unemployed, illiterates, etc.). Social welfare organizations are active in the area of neighbourhood mediation, youth work, social participation, social work, parental support, and domestic work. Patients and employees were also recruited from the hospital (EMC).

Additionally, collaborations with loco-regional organizations with strong cultural, industrial or historical roots were established, as is the case of the coal miners' associations in Asturias. In this region, the mining activity was the main source of income during the last century and many citizens have a strong feeling of belonging to this association, favouring recruitment among its members.

Finally, organized volunteer networks are of enormous support as they often provide services to the most disadvantaged of society and they exist in all countries. Their special sensitivity to issues of marginalization and proximity to vulnerable people transform them into valuable allies for the project.

Table 6 represents the information on collaborating entities from civil society.

Table 6. Alliances with Civil Society in EFFICHRONIC

Partner	Stakeholder
SESPA/CSPA/FICYT	Mineworkers trade union 'Montepio'
	Associations of Roma people 'UNGA', 'Secretariado Gitano'
	Neighbourhood associations in several cities over the territory
	Association of people with mental health problems and family 'AFESA'
	Association of carers 'AZVASE'
CHUM	Federation of hearing impaired of Asturias 'FESOPRAS'
	Trade Union 'Sydel du Pays Coeur d'Hérault'
	Patient association 'AFM-Téléthon'
	Patient association 'AFPRic
QISMET	Volunteer networks of collaborating stakeholders
EMC	Social Wellbeing organisations: DOCK, WMO Radar and Zorgbelang Brabant
	Volunteer organisation 'UVV'
EOG	Liguria Alzheimer Association
	Hospital Volunteer Association 'AVO'
	Several trade unions (CGIL-SPI, UILP and CISL-FNP)

4.3.5 Others strategies

In the Netherlands, recruitment was also carried out in community places: in libraries, social work organisation, swimming pool, supermarkets... using flyers and, importantly, door-to-door recruitment, which resulted in a very effective technique for sampling specific populations focussing on their geographical coverage.

4.4 Results of the CDSMP intervention.

This section describes the achieved results of the programme implementation at all sites, from M6 to M34. It needs to be pointed out that most sites have been experiencing a backlog in receiving all data as other entities were involved in the implementation: providers, stakeholders and leaders. Some information, mostly related to the number of collected questionnaires, is still underway, and the final numbers will be included in D6.2 “EFFICHRONIC evidence based results and health economy analysis report” which is due in September 2020.

The reflected information has been extracted from the reports the partners provide to the coordination team every 2 months and the periodic virtual and face-to-face meetings of the consortium. The evolution of the implementation was monitored by the coordination team throughout the process and at the meetings mitigation measures were discussed and implemented where needed.

1. Number of workshops

At the end of the implementation period, Spain reached the highest number of delivered CDSMP workshops with 85 series, followed by the Netherlands with 51, UK (40), Italy (31) and France (29). In total 236 CDSMP workshops were delivered. In figure 1, the distribution of workshops is reflected graphically.

Figure 1. EFFICHRONIC: Distribution of the number of workshops

The average number of engaged participants per workshop was calculated based on the total number average number of 13, and in the Netherlands the workshops had an average of 12 participants (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Average number of engaged CDSMP participants per workshop

2. Participants

Figure 3 shows a schematic diagram of the recruitment process in the framework of the Project EFFICHRONIC.

Figure 3. Flow recruitment in EFFICHRONIC

In total, **2951** vulnerable persons with chronic conditions and caregivers have been engaged in EFFICHRONIC, surpassing generously the needed 2000 individuals as indicated in the project proposal. The number of **participants finishing the programme is of 2317**. In figure 4 the number of engaged participants and participants who finished is reflected graphically for each site.

Figure 4. Comparison of the number of engaged participants and finished the CDSMP

Based on the difference between the number of starting and finishing participants, the percentage of successful accomplishment of CDSMP workshops in the framework of EFFICHRONIC was calculated. The overall proportion of participants who attend a minimum of four out of six sessions is 79%, which is only slightly lower than the target of 80% as was defined in Specific Objective 3. In figure 5 the relation between starting and finishing participants is reflected at all sites. The graphic shows that there are some differences between countries. Spain and the UK, that had an existing network of leaders and experience in implementing the programme, achieved the highest success rates together with France. In the Netherlands, a lack of adequate information during the recruitment causing misunderstandings and false expectations in the participants is mentioned as a factor contributing to the early drop-out by Dutch interviewees.

Figure 5. Loss of workshop participants at each pilot site and average value for CDSMP

Figure 6 shows the percentage of received baseline and selfy-MPI questionnaires of the engaged participants at each site and in total. The highest percentage was reached by France. The lower rates in Spain can be explained by the participation of highly vulnerable groups, such as in prison and in Roma communities, where the data collection was not possible. Given the fact that these participants were not considered for quantitative analysis and the programme had a significant impact of them, some of their testimonies will be included in future qualitative studies.

Figure 6. EFFICHRONIC: Received Baseline and Selfy-MPI Questionnaires

An overview of the achieved results at all sites and in total are reflected in table 7.

Table 7. EFFICHRONIC: Overview of the implementation results

	Spain	France*	UK	NL**	Italy	EFFICHRONIC
Nº workshops***	85	29	40	51	31	236
Engaged participants	1131	231	577	612	400	2951
Participants finished	932	174	502	425	284	2317
Baseline questionnaires	515	183	346	382	280	1706
Selfy-MPI	424	184	316	351	270	1545

*In France, workshops were still being conducted when this report was written. The data for the number of engaged participants is of 28 workshops (one was still to start in March 2020), while the number of baseline questionnaires and people who finished workshops is for 24 of the 29 workshops with 200 people starting.

**In the Netherlands, an additional 30 citizens completed baseline questionnaires but did not sign informed consent and they are not included in the total number of questionnaires.

***Due to the coronavirus crisis three workshops have been cancelled in Spain, and another three in France, in February and March. The data from those workshops have not been included in the deliverable.

3. Timely evolution of the implementation of CDSMP workshop series

Figure 7 shows graphically when workshops were delivered from May 2018 to March 2020, and how between all, the objectives of the implementation were reached.

Figure 7. Cumulative evolution of number of workshops during project implementation

4.5 Key Performance Indicators

In this report, the corresponding KPI are summarised in table 8. All the objectives have been reached and the target numbers of individuals reached, engaged and trained have been widely exceeded as described before. The successful accomplishment rate in the programme was slightly lower than expected but in contrast, the number of engaged and trained people (or people who finished) exceeds the targets. Thus, the losses are sufficiently compensated by training more people than expected.

Table 8. EFFICHRONIC: KPIs related to the implementation

CSDMP Implementation	Target	Achieved	%
Individuals reached during the communication-recruitment phase	200.000	906.000*	100%
Individuals engaged in EFFICHRONIC (400 per country)	2000	2951	100%
Individuals trained in EFFICHRONIC (400 per country)	2000	2317	100%
Countries where EFFICHRONIC is implemented	5	5	100%

Facilitators recruited (32 per country)	160	>160	100%
Patients suffering from or at risk at chronic disease recruited	2000	2951	100%
Global learning outcomes. Percentage of successful accomplishment	80%	79,4%	98,8%
Experimental mortality rate	<20%	20,6%	98,8%

* This is a rough estimate. Data from the General Mass Media Survey could not be obtained

4.6 Qualitative evaluation of the recruitment strategies

Below are the main conclusions of the qualitative approach:

- All partners tried to engage health care organizations, social care organizations and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs).
- In the case of the UK, the existing network of CDSMP providers in the whole territory conducted the recruitment with the guidance of QISMET. The providers themselves represented a broad variety of health care organisations, social care organisations and CSOs.
- The most active entity in recruiting multipliers and engaging them as a part of the participatory approach within the EFFICHRONIC project was the Public Healthcare Service in Asturias SESPA: the SESPA enjoys a particularly advantaged position within the consortium, being itself a public administration. It facilitates contact and coordination with other regional administration officers (e.g., social workers) and to reach CSOs more effectively thanks to the previous work conducted in these areas.
- In the Netherlands, the involvement of CSOs resulted in a sub-optimal result. The recruitment was performed in community places: in libraries, social work organisation, swimming pool, supermarkets... using flyers and, importantly, door-to-door recruitment, which resulted in a very effective technique for sampling specific populations focussing on their geographical coverage. Direct recruitment and engagement of participants worked well in this case; however, it is considered, as it has been mentioned, sub-optimal. More human resources for conducting this direct networking strategy (Time-Space Recruitment Technique) would be needed, as well as a longer period for implementation. It is noticeable that EMC would like to recruit directly from the hospital staff, without involving multipliers and CSOs, centralising all tasks but having more resources available.
- The engagement of CSOs and other professionals – specifically, social workers- worked very well in rural settings in France. France also conducted an aggressive involvement of multipliers through events, workshops and specific communication means, resulting in stable alliances with those

professionals and associations. France raised the engagement of participants by providing them with transport vouchers and other benefits, reaching a surprisingly low drop-out rate that 13 %.

- Italy engaged associations and municipalities: the huge impact of snowball sampling⁴ and recruitment should be highlighted. It appears to be the most effective recruitment strategy for the interviewed persons. For facilitating the engagement of CSOs they required more “traditional” information about the CDSMP and its impact and advantages for chronic patients. To plan a good enough snowball strategy would need more time and, also, more human resources.

- A longer period of implementation and more human resources for conducting the networking strategy of EFFICHRONIC have been identified as key aspects for achieving a successful engagement and recruitment plan. Also, in the UK and Italy, the length and repetitiveness of the questionnaires, and the sensitive data collected, were identified as the triggers of the participant’s drop-out. On the other hand, the issue of certifications of attendance and the delivery of vouchers for lunch or similar benefits increased the engagement of the participants

- Also, the personality factors of participants were raised as an issue during the interviews: some persons might be shy or insecure in participating, if the programme is specifically conducted with psycho-socially vulnerable populations, then cultural, and also gender, determinants should be considered.

- Systemic factors, such as the Hospital-centred Model – which includes potential tokenism and paternalistic approaches that may be underlying the considerations about the health literacy and self-management programmes, in general - are also highlighted as an issue. In addition, CSOs might consider that they are helping the institution implementing the EFFICHRONIC project, instead of considering a win-win situation where all parties involved give and receive: for example, access to the hard-to-reach population is given, and health education and literacy are received, etc. Competing interests could be also considered: e.g., some CSOs already have their own health literacy programmes.

- In addition, a lack of adequate information during the recruitment leading to misunderstood and false expectations in the participants is mentioned as a factor contributing to the early drop-out by French, Spanish and Dutch interviewees. Of course, considering that EFFICHRONIC targets patients with chronic conditions, exacerbations and illnesses are also cause of early drop-out and programme abandonment.

Lessons learned from the qualitative approach

- The duration of the recruitment and implementation is the most important factor that affects the recruitment and participation of vulnerable people. Six more months have been enough to recruit the target population.

⁴Snowball sampling is where research participants recruit other participants for a test or study. It is used where potential participants are hard to find

- The need for more resources (mainly human resources) for conducting the networking strategy seems to be the second most important issue to consider. The task is time consuming as contacts with stakeholders must be repeated and maintained.
- The length of the questionnaires, repetitiveness of questions and sensitivity of the collected data at the beginning of the workshops, puts some participants off from attending and even puts the implementation at risk and increases the abandonment rate.
- If the programme is carried out with psychosocially vulnerable populations, also cultural and gender determinants must be observed.
- Finding and raising leadership within organizations and also among participants is a success factor in recruitment. In addition, finding participants from the same social context as the participants who are able to transmit the benefits of the CDSMP intervention is a success trigger.
- Systemic factors are highlighted, such as the hospital-centered model, and therefore, the potential tokenism and paternalism approaches that can be the basis for considerations of health literacy and self-management programs in general.
- It has been identified that some CSOs could consider that they are helping the institution to implement the EFFICHRONIC project, instead of considering a situation of mutual benefit in which all the parties involved give and receive: Access to the hard-to-reach population is provided, and health education and literacy. are received, etc.
- A weakening element is that there might be competing interests: for example, some CSOs already have their own health literacy programmes.
- In addition, the lack of adequate information during recruitment that leads to erroneous expectations and misunderstandings in participants is mentioned as a contributing factor to the early abandonment of French and Spanish respondents.
- Given that EFFICHRONIC is aimed at people with chronic conditions, exacerbations and diseases are also the cause of early abandonment and abandonment of the programme.
- It is possible that the participation of caregivers in the project has a positive influence on recruitment. It is essential to involve family caregivers for the recruitment of the elderly in research projects, including those living in institutions.
- In addition, the community approach is consistent with the strategies described in a review of the literature that shows that community agents, such as navigators, community health workers, lay workers or support partners, are recognized assets to involve groups of difficult access in health interventions.

SECTION 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings in relation to the defined objectives in this report are the following:

1. **Sample recruitment in the 5 countries according to the designed strategies.**

More than 2951 participants distributed over the five countries have been successfully engaged in a CDSMP workshop during the 18 months of project implementation. This has been achieved through the mixture of recruitment strategies and the high number of involved entities.

2. **Preparation of the intervention programme.**

All pilot sites trained the necessary number of leaders per pilot (32) required to conduct the workshops in the community, and even exceed the objective: more than 234 leaders were trained. Where necessary, the sites also adapted the programme material to be able to implement the intervention in their territory. The dissemination activities and recruitment strategies contributed to the successful preparation of the programme.

3. **Implementation of the CDSMP.**

People with chronic conditions and caregivers from the following vulnerable groups attended the programme: ethnic minorities, immigrants, refugees, elderly people living alone or in institutions, people with few economic resources or living in therapeutic communities, inmates, and members of many associations. In total, 2951 people started the training and 2317 finished four out of six sessions, meaning a loss of 21% of the expected.

4. **Qualitative evaluation of the recruitment strategies:** the study provides another insight into the implementation, and highlights the importance of human factors and logistic circumstances from the recruitment coordinators' point of view.

The following **recommendations** present the strengths and weaknesses derived from the implementation process:

1. **Necessity of extra time in the implementation phase:** The foreseen project lifetime was not sufficient to implement a CDSMP programme in vulnerable populations in five countries and reach a sample size of 2000 people. The 12 months that were foreseen were not sufficient to prepare the intervention, recruit the study population and implement the intervention. A project extension of 6 months was needed to successfully accomplish the objectives.
2. **Effective mitigation actions.** The different starting points from the partners has been a rich source of learning. Strengths and weaknesses of the recruitment strategies were rapidly identified

and all study sites have been capable of implementing effective mitigation actions to reach the objectives despite the difficulties.

- 3. Differences in results at different sites as a consequence of different starting situations and unforeseen obstacles:** the different organizational structures of the EFFICHRONIC partners require them to adapt the theoretical framework to their specific reality, adding a complementary dimension to the project. To reach the target population, all partners had to leave their comfort zone to create alliances with organizations and population groups they usually do not work with. By doing this, they succeeded in connecting to the most needed of society and handing them the tools to improve their self-management.
- 4. A key success factor: the strategic coordination of agents with different backgrounds -** healthcare, social work and community - and at different levels - ministries, city councils and associations – that worked together coordinated at the local-regional level to obtain maximum recruitment results. A great variety of key agents from different sectors in the territories must be engaged in the recruitment process. The simultaneous implementation of the various strategies and the effective coordination led by the project management team have been fundamental pillars for achieving and optimizing the results of the training programme.

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ANNEX 1: MOTIVATED REPORT FOR THE PROJECT'S EXTENSION REQUEST

Motivated report

for the six months extension

request of EFFICHRONIC

EFFICHRONIC has received funding from the European Union's Health Programme (2014-2020) under Grant Agreement 738127

Asturias, 23 July 2019

EXTENSION REPORT

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Motivated report for the six months extension request of EFFICHRONIC

At the fourth face-to-face meeting of EFFICHRONIC project in Rotterdam on the 2nd and 3rd of May 2019, the possibility of asking for an extension of the project was discussed, as two of the partners previously suggested this. The proposal was voted by all the consortium members at this General Assembly meeting, and the result of the vote to request a six months extension was in favour.

In our first communication with the Project Officer, the reasons and argumentation to request an extension were the following:

- 1. Ensuring a sample size that allows a statistically significant analysis of the evaluation framework parameters and ensure the cost-effectiveness analysis.***

Current situation:

One of the biggest problems we encounter in the project is the difficulty to have the baseline and follow-up questionnaires filled out by the vulnerable target population. In order to ensure statistical power, 978 questionnaires must be collected at 6 months post-intervention. Considering a 20 percent sample loss (estimate based on literature data), we have to ensure the collection of 1236 baseline questionnaires.

Currently we have collected 758 filled-in baseline questionnaires between all partners. This means that we still need to collect 478 more, which is a very high number considering that the training sessions, according to the current planning, have to end in September and furthermore, during summer holidays, less or no workshops will be facilitated.

We would also like to point out that the beginning of the project in the month of June has conditioned the schedule initially projected in EFFICHRONIC. To start, this caused a delay in beginning with any project activities during the first year, and currently, it is precisely the months of summer break that are needed to reach the sample population with a comfortable margin.

Advantage of the extension:

By creating the possibility of organizing workshops in the last quarter of the year (until December 2019), the period after the summer with greater general and labour activity would be optimized. This way, the minimum number of 1236 baseline questionnaires could be reached and even passed, which could compensate a higher than 20 percent drop-out rate of the vulnerable population. Having the time to collect a bigger number of questionnaires would ensure sufficient statistical power for data analysis.

2. Achieving greater homogeneity of the sample population.

Current situation:

The progress of the programme implementation shows substantial differences between the partners, mainly related to whether or not they had experience in the Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme previously to EFFICHRONIC. Some partners had to translate the programme material and organize leaders trainings first, while others could start facilitating workshops immediately. For instance, the partner in the Netherlands collected 43 baseline questionnaires while Spain gathered 309 forms.

Furthermore, the late approval of the Ethics Committee at the French study site caused the implementation to start six months later than scheduled in France.

Advantage of the extension:

Allowing more time for programme implementation would give those countries, which are now in the optimal situation to implement (having the necessary material and leaders available), the opportunity to further implement the programme in their territories. Furthermore, it would benefit obtaining a more representative sample from each of the five pilot countries.

Based on the previous arguments, we would like to request a project extension of six months (without economic compensation), in order to increase not only the representativeness of all pilots in a more homogeneous way, but also the amount of collected data, which will ensure a greater impact of the results.

Of the requested extension, three months will be exclusively dedicated to further implement the programme and increase the necessary sample population as described below. The other three months of the extension period will be mostly invested in collecting the follow-up questionnaires at 6 months post-intervention and for collecting all data from the partners and data cleaning. The experience we have at this stage of the project with collecting the follow-up forms is that it takes more time and effort than expected beforehand. This point is key in obtaining quality data to determine the impact of the intervention.

Thus, the six months extension will be designated to reach the stipulated sample size by implementing the intervention further, to collect the follow-up questionnaires and to data cleaning, all in order to generate statistically significant impact data.

In D2.3 "Communication and dissemination evaluation report", the carried out Communication and Dissemination (C&D) actions are described, which were mainly aimed at participant recruitment. Furthermore, the analysis of the performed activities led to the development of some recommendations for all partners to enhance the C&D campaign.

On request of the coordination team, all partners provided a report describing the planned measures that will be taken in the extension period, in order to reach the required sample size. These reports are reflected in the following pages almost literally as received, to not lose information in the intent to format and homogenize the text.

Corrective Actions from partners

FICYT-CSPA-SESPA, Asturias, Spain

In Asturias, we will continue to put into practice the following activities, in order to minimize the loss of participants and thus increase the effectiveness of the C&D strategy:

1. A communication campaign specifically directed to vulnerable people

A multichannel communication campaign is organized to reach vulnerable people and, most importantly, aimed at reaching key multipliers who are able to maximize the impact. This campaign includes different news posts and articles in traditional press and on online channels about the implementation of the CDSMP in different settings, such as the regional prison, Roma associations, NGO's or organizations working with immigrants.

The target groups and objectives for this campaign are:

- **Service-users:** patients suffering from highly prevalent chronic diseases and informal carers, not directly involved in the EFFICHRONIC project.
 - To raise the health literacy and self-caring abilities among the targeted population including people not yet involved in the project workshops in order to ensure a broad and meaningful social impact, also counting on word-of-mouth marketing
 - To provide service-users already participating in the workshops with additional resources and information
- **Civil society:** NGOs, patients' advocates, associations, etc.
 - To provide tools and information to associations, NGOs, patients or vulnerable persons' advocates and other multipliers in order to implement new initiatives to increase the health literacy of their end-users.
 - To gather ideas and key information to recruit and engage more service-users, thanks to the networking with collaborating organisations and their multiplier potential.
- **General public:**
 - To inform the general society about the CDSMP and how health literacy has a significant impact on public health.

In order to have a higher impact through mass media, material from the previously prepared press kit will keep on being used:

- Leaflets describing the project in detail in Spanish.
- High-resolution logo and additional images that are used to publish press releases and notes, articles and other news posts.
- Videos and other dissemination material already prepared in Spanish.

- Compilation of press appearances.

The Asturian team will keep on performing C&D activities similar to the ones described in D2.3 and will intensify them to reach the planned objectives. These actions include:

- Offline and online networking to reach civil society entities.
- Attending social and health care fairs or other kinds of events related to vulnerability or chronic diseases.
- Appearances in paper and online magazines and newspapers.
- Social media interaction.
- Appearances on local radio and TV.

Furthermore, the communication campaign will also take into account gender, age and sociocultural background of the target groups, as this might determine the use of different communication channels. The proposed resources were selected to be able to reach the highest number of persons in the most cost-effective way, using the already available contacts and media.

The content of the communications will be on implementation of the programme and also on specific initiatives and the impact on the different targeted communities, such as people from the Roma or immigrant community, new vulnerable families, people who live isolated, or inmates.

Table 1 shows some of the possible actions of the communication campaign for the coming months as planned by the Asturian team.

Table 1: EFFICHRONIC specific communication campaign in Asturias 2019-2020

Date	Possible title	Target	Means
September 2019	The implementation of a Health Literacy and Education programme in the Asturian prison	Civil society	Direct networking (online and offline), events
16/9/2019-28/9/2019	The implementation of a Health Literacy and Education programme in the Asturian prison	General public	Traditional newspapers , Local TV, Social Media (Facebook, Twitter)
7/10/2019-11/10/2019	How Health Literacy impacts on Public Health	Service users	Online magazines/newspapers, traditional newspapers , Local TV, Social Media
30/9/2019-11/10/2019	Activism through evidence: New horizons on health literacy and education for NGOs and advocates	Civil society	Online magazines, social media.
4/11/2019 - 8/11/2019	Caring for the carer	General public and	Traditional newspapers and local TV or radio

		service-users	
11/10/2019-15/11/2019	The SESPA ¹ promotes self-care in rural communities	General public and service-users	Traditional newspapers and local TV or radio
13/1/2020-17/1/2020	What is EFFICHRONIC and the CDSMP?	General public and service-users	Traditional newspapers
10/2/2020 - 14/2/2020	Self-management of chronic diseases and empowerment in the Roma community in Asturias	General public and service-users	Newspapers Local TV (third parties' social media channels and other communication tools)
March 2020	Engaging your community and spreading the word among the general society!	Civil society	Direct face-to-face networking and organization of a workshop to gather experiences and ideas. Online communication activity

2. Continuous networking with stakeholders and planned workshops

The stakeholders involved in EFFICHRONIC in Asturias are many and varied as previously described in D2.3. After months of working together, the established collaborations with associations of Roma people, immigrants, carers with low economic resources, therapeutic communities, NGOs, social workers and city hall staff have been consolidated and will continue during the final trimester of 2019. As a result, at least 12 series of workshops are planned for the referred period as described in Table 2. The estimates of the number of participants are based on the results of past workshops.

Table 2: Planned EFFICHRONIC workshops in Asturias Sept-Dec 2019

Nº	Period	Stakeholder	Estimation of engaged participants (starting a programme)	Estimation of participants attending ≥ 4 sessions	Estimation of questionnaires from participants attending ≥ 4 sessions
1	Sept – Oct 2019	Prison of Asturias. UTE1	15	13	12
2	Sept – Oct 2019	Prison of Asturias. UTE2	15	13	12
3	Nov – Dec 2019	Prison of Asturias. UTE1	15	13	12
4	Nov – Dec 2019	Prison of Asturias. UTE2	15	13	12
5	Oct - Nov 2019	Prison of Asturias. CIS	15	12	12
6	Sept – Oct 2019	Association of	14	8	0

¹ Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias

		Roma people - UNGA			
7	Nov – Dec 2019	Association of Roma people - UNGA	14	8	0
8	Sept – Oct 2019	Therapeutic Community “La Santina”	18	14	10
9	Nov – Dec 2019	Therapeutic Community “La Santina”	18	14	10
10	Sept – Oct 2019	NGO working with immigrants - ACCEM	15	8	8
11	Oct - Nov 2019	Centre for the elderly – Social Services Pumarín. Oviedo	15	13	10
12	Sept – Oct 2019	Centre for the elderly – Social Services Gijón	15	13	10
13	Oct-Nov 2019	Cáritas-Avilés	15	8	8
Total forecast Sept-Dec 2019			199	150	116
Data from previous workshops (52)			597	525	402
Foreseen final totals Asturias			796	675	518

3. Procedure to collect the follow-up questionnaires

The following procedure has been established to minimize the possible loss of follow-up data in Asturias.

1. The participant is called up by phone to inform him/her that the follow-up questionnaire will be sent by ordinary mail. A stamped return envelope is included.
2. Shipping of the questionnaire to the participant.
3. Waiting period of a month to receive back the filled-out questionnaire.
4. In case a form is not returned, the coordination team advises the corresponding workshop leader or recruiter of the lack of response of the particular participant and provides them with their contact details.
5. The workshop leader or recruiter contacts the person and asks the participant to fill out the form and send it back. A new form is sent in case of necessity. In case the participant denies collaboration, or it is not possible to contact him/her, this is registered by the coordination team.

By means of the planned C&D and implementation activities and the procedure to collect the follow-up questionnaires, the Asturian team intends to reach to the maximum the objectives and the KPI's related to reaching the study sample in EFFICHRONIC.

EOG, Genoa, Italy

1. C&D and recruitment plan from September to December 31, 2019.

To date EOG has enrolled 256 participants (numbers of signed informed consents), among them 213 participants attended at least one session and 190 participants attended at least 4 sessions (so we collected 190 baseline questionnaires) and we have already started to collect the follow up questionnaires.

In order to reach the sample size as stated in the proposal we have decided to plan further dissemination and recruitment strategies:

- **June - September** further communications to all associations already engaged in the D&C activities that have already sent participants or have showed interest in participating or disseminating the CDSMP.
- From **September to December** 2019 new communication and dissemination activities will be performed as during in the past months (meetings at the Hospital with citizens, meeting with associations, Social Media, News in the Journals) especially for the CDSMPs that will be organised for the citizens inside the Hospital, because for the others workshops we have already been performing several meeting inside the place they will be performed by the end of September.

2. Schedule of the planned workshops

Table 3: Planned EFFICHRONIC workshops in Italy Sept-Dec 2019

Workshops already planned	Where	start	end	N° of participant expected
1	Genoa Municipality	19/09/2019	24/10/2019	20
2	Genoa Municipality	26/09/2019	31/10/2019	20
3	EOG Hospital	25/09/2019	6/11/2019	20
4	Local association	30/09/2019	4/11/2019	15
5	EOG Hospital	01/10/2019	05/11/2019	10
6	EOG Hospital	10/10/2019	14/11/2019	10
7	EOG Hospital	12/11/2019	17/12/2019	10
8	EOG Hospital	14/11/2019	19/12/19	20
9	EOG Hospital	13/11/2019	18/12/2019	10
Total				135
Workshops to be defined	Where	Start	End	N° of participants expected
1	Local Schools	September 2019	October 2019	15
2	Local association	October 2019	November 2019	15

3	Campomorone Municipality	September 2019	October 2019	15
4	EOG Hospital	October 2019	November 2019	10
5	Care Home	October/November 2019	November/december 2019	10
Total				65

3. Risk plan with some contingency measures

Through C&D activities we planned to have the opportunity to reach new stakeholders and participants interested in attending workshops. Moreover workshops already planned will give us the opportunity to reach new participants (our experience is that word of mouth is the best dissemination and recruitment strategy).

In September and October 2019 during specific Congress (“Alzheimer day”- September 21st and “elderly and drug” October 10th and 11th) EOG will have the opportunity to present the EFFICHRONIC project to health professionals, stakeholders (associations, municipalities...) and citizens.

New collaborations with General Practitioners have been already planned due to a SIGOT project designed to implement the evaluation of the frailty in elderly.

And finally as EOG we have been participating with the University of Genoa (Sociology Department), the University of the Third Age and an Association for Fragile Elderly People to a project regarding the promotion of the resilience in the elderly where the CDSMP could be an action, among others, to promote the resilience in elderly people and elderly caregivers recruited.

CHUM, Montpellier, France

1. New locations and communication campaign

In order to achieve the sample size, we have planned to increase the number of cities/villages where the CDSMP is proposed. We have planned a new Leaders training for the following dates: 29-30/08 and 5-6/09/2019. During this training, 12 to 14 new Leaders will be certificated allowing to spread the program in new locations and to include new stakeholders in the project (Figure 1).

Figure 1: France: Locations where the CDSMP is implemented (in red) and where CDSMP will be proposed starting from September 2019 (in purple)

At the same time a massive communication campaign will be performed to improve the awareness of the project. The communication campaign and the recruitment is planned in Occitanie as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Communication campaign and recruitment plan in Occitanie (France)

Time	Action/Key Message	Target	Means
29-30/08/ 2019 et 5- 6/09/2019	New leaders training	Laypersons and health professionals (12-14 persons)	Propose the CDSMP in new locations and engagement of new stakeholders
August- September	Online campaigns via the local website and local Twitter account	Potential participants	Recruitment
September	Press release "More than 100 people have already benefited from the CDSMP"	Laypersons and service-users (all) and health professionals	Traditional newspapers and specialized newspapers to arise awareness and promote recruitment
19/09/2019	EFFICHRONIC and the CDSMP in Occitanie	Laypersons (> 60 years old) and disable persons <i>(Conseil Départemental de l'Hérault)</i>	Face-to-face meeting with the organization that is in charge of this target group to promote recruitment
September	Face-to Face meetings in retirement homes	Potential participants	Recruitment
September	Face-to Face meetings in therapeutic centers	Potential participants	Recruitment
September	Face-to Face with associations involved with vulnerable persons	Potential participants	Recruitment
Monthly	Newsletter to the leaders	Leaders of the CDSMP	Build a network and encourage their implication
Monthly	Newsletter to the stakeholders	Stakeholders (Civil society)	Encourage their implication
Monthly	Visit pharmacies located in the vulnerable areas	Potential participants	Recruit through the pharmacies
Weekly	Traditional newspaper insertion	Potential participants	Recruitment
04/11/2019	"The implementation of CDSMP in Occitanie"	Health professionals <i>(ARS - Agence</i>	Recruitment and awareness of the project in others zones

		Régionale de Santé)	of the Occitanie region
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2. Schedule of future workshops

Thanks to the communication strategy as well as to the recruitment plan we will be able to plan the following workshops and to reach the sample size required (Table 5).

Table 5: Schedule of the Workshops Sept- Dec 2019, France

Number	Period/dates	Location	Number of participants (projections min-max)
1	11/09/2019-16/10/2019	Perpignan (AFM-Téléthon)	10-15
2	September	CHU Montpellier	10-15
3	September	Therapeutic center in Montpellier "Le Melezet"	10-15
4	September	Montpellier vulnerable area	10-12
5	September	Grau du Roi	10-15
6	September	Alès	8-12
7	September	Lodève	8-12
8	October	Perpignan	10-15
9	October	Nimes	10-15
10	October	Toulouse	10-12
11	October	Clermont l'Hérault	8-12
12	October	Retirement home	10-12
13	November	Alès	8-12
14	November	Montpellier vulnerable area	10-15
15	November	Toulouse	10-15
16	November	Nimes	10-12
17	December	Perpignan	10-12

18	December	Lunel	10-12
19	December	Nimes	10-15
20	December	CHU Montpellier	10-12
21	December	Toulouse	10-15
TOTAL participants			202-282
TOTAL participants (including the workshops already done)			319-399

So far, 117 participants took part in the CDSMP and 106 participants completed the programme (at least 4 workshops attended), giving a completion rate of 91%. We expect that on 202-282 new participants, 184-257 will complete de program, giving a total of 290-362 participants that attended to at least 4 workshops. All the participants who completed the program also completed all the questionnaires, normally we will have 290-362 baseline questionnaires.

3. Contingency plan

In case the number of workshops/participants cannot be reached as a contingency measure, we will revised the communication and recruitment plan to improve/refocus the message of our communication campaign in order to optimize the engagement and recruitment during the implementation of the program. In addition, we will plan a monthly meeting (physical or virtual) with the leaders and most involved stakeholders in order to gather their ideas and to motivate them.

QISMET, United Kingdom

In the UK, the provision of CDSMP programmes for the EFFICHRONIC Project is undertaken by 7 independent providers. They recruit vulnerable individuals to attend programmes that they organise on our behalf.

We have now got 160 Baseline/Selfy questionnaires and 60 follow ups (as at June 2019) and are on course to receive at least 240 of the former by December 2019 and 216 of the latter by June 2019. We are finding that we are achieving a very high follow up rate of about 90% (ie 90% of people who completed the initial questionnaires are also completing the six month questionnaire). This is due to the way that we have structured the payments to the providing organisations ie they only get paid if they supply all 3 questionnaires (2 in the case of carers). The incentive is therefore there to provide the follow-up questionnaires.

We have had about 350 people start workshops so far, and are on course to have had about 500 by December 2019.

We have provided communication and dissemination support to our providers, such as press releases and also help with advising how best to get the questionnaires completed. We feel that this will now enable us to meet the extended time targets.

Due to the nature of our contracts with our providers, it is up to them when they put programmes on in order to meet local need. However we know that there will be at least 10 programmes commencing between now and the end of December 2019: 2 a month excluding August. Each programme will start with an average of 15 people i.e. 150 in total.

We are keeping a very close watch over programmes and numbers of participants and questionnaires received. The numbers given here tend to understate the true position as we received details of numbers in arrears, in some cases a month after a programme has finished: but we will be aware if the results do not meet our targets early on.

If we see that this is happening we have a couple of providers in reserve who can quickly join the project and provide us with the extra numbers needed.

EMC, Rotterdam, the Netherlands

The number of citizens engaged in CDSMP has been running behind schedule. Reasons include:

- 1) Fewer participants per workshop session;
- 2) Difficulties in encouraging trainers to train more than one series of workshops;
- 3) Difficulties in recruiting citizens. It is our aim to reach the target number 3 months later than the initial deadline of patient inclusion.

Corrective actions include:

- 1) Recruitment of more trainers;
- 2) Finding new sources to recruit participants;
- 3) The appointment of more dedicated staff on the project.

We will train 20 new trainers early September, who will each train 2 series of citizen workshops from Sep-Dec 2019. We will only train trainers who have explicitly told us they are willing and available to train two series of workshops in this period. Thus, 20 series of workshops will follow from this new group of trainers. We aim at workshop sizes of 20 citizens, but from experience we know that that is hard to reach. Therefore, considering a drop-out of 10% of the trainers (18 trainers left) and a workshop size of 15, we will engage $18 \times 15 = 270$ citizens.

In addition, we have planned workshops using existing trainers in the period Jun-Dec 2019. Unfortunately, opportunities to make them train new groups are restricted, but we aim at 10 series of workshops. Hence $10 \times 15 = 150$ citizens.

We will continue the recruitment strategy as used before; there are 3 main sources. The first is the employees and patients from the Erasmus MC, the second is the network of the trainers we have trained so far (including 4 municipal organizations who are active in the area of neighborhood mediation, youth work, societal participation, social work, parental support and domestic work). The third source is the announcement of workshops at public places by means of flyers and/or posters (supermarkets, pharmacies etc).

Additionally, a new recruitment source is the network of the Municipality of Rotterdam. We started engaging the Municipality in June 2019. The Municipality has direct access to 15000 potential participants with low educational levels. The recruitment from this source has already started.

Apart from the recruitment of trainers and citizens, we have changed the encouragement of completing the questionnaires. We emphasize the importance of the questionnaire to trainers before starting the training and have dedicated a dedicated person to chase after the questionnaires.

We scheduled 4 series of workshops in June, 2 in July, 2 in August, 8 in September, 4 in October, 4 in November and 4 in December.

We may increase the number of workshops in Oct-Dec 2019.

Conclusions

As described in the previous section, a major effort will be made between all partners to fully benefit from the extension period to not only reach the promised sample size, but also to collect as many follow-up questionnaires as possible and to clean the data, increasing this way the quality of the data to perform the data analysis.

Numerous communication activities, meetings with stakeholders, additional leaders trainings are only some the proposed measures to increase the number of workshops in the coming months.

It is estimated that, by the end of the project and taking into account the extension period of six months, 2631 people will have been engaged in the programme and 1906 baseline questionnaires will have been collected between all partners.

Furthermore, the proportion of engaged patients will be more equalized between all partners and the partners that were running more behind, are planning a bigger catch up movement to reach the required figures.

The foreseen measures will ensure a sample size big enough to provide statistical power and to generate solid results from the implementation of the CDSMP in vulnerable population in five European countries. The table below summarizes the results per partner after the extension (Table 6).

Table 6: Summary of the results after the extension

	Engaged participants committed in the GA	Total engaged participants achieved after the extension	Baseline questionnaires (considering drop-out)
FICYT-CSPA-SESPA	400	796	518
EOG	400	413	368
CHUM	400	399	362
QISMET	400	500	240
EMC	400	523	418
TOTAL	2000	2631	1906

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ANNEX 2: STRATEGIES FOR IDENTIFYING AND RECRUITING HARD-TO-REACH POPULATIONS

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DISCUSSION PAPER

EFFICHRONIC PROJECT

**STRATEGIES FOR IDENTIFYING AND RECRUITING
HARD-TO-REACH POPULATIONS. ABRIL 2017**

1. EFFICHRONIC

EFFICHRONIC - which stands for Enhancing health systems suitability by providing cost-efficiency data of evidenced based Interventions for chronic management in stratified population based on clinical socio-economic determinants of health - is a European project financed within the III Health Programme (2017-2020) which brings together a consortium of European health organizations under the coordination of the Foundation for the Promotion in Asturias of Applied Scientific Research and Technology (FICYT) and the Regional Ministry of Health of Asturias.

The main goal of EFFICHRONIC is to provide evidence on the positive return of investment and relevant data on cost- efficiency of the application of the Chronic Disease Self- Management Programme (CDSMP) in 5 different European countries (France, Italy, The Netherlands, Spain and the UK) with a special focus on those factors (health & medical related, social, cultural, economic) affecting chronic disorders in key populations. The CDSMP which has been developed by the Stanford University, seeks to train chronic patients to empower them to self-manage their condition, to take control of their disease and to improve access to health services. This will led to better health outcomes.

To meet this overall goal, EFFICHRONIC pursues the following main objectives:

1. To carry out multidimensional analysis and stratification methodologies to identify vulnerable groups/individuals in Spain, France, Italy, The Netherlands and the UK involved to maximise the impact of the CDSMP when implemented.
2. To design specific strategies to reach the targeted individual/groups identified/stratified to involve them in the implementation of the programme.
3. To implement the programme in 5 regions of 5 European countries through the adherence of at least 500 individuals of the stratified/identified populations in each setting (N=2500).
4. To generate a comprehensive framework to i) assess the impact by using cost- efficiency and health economics techniques and ii) implement specific methodologies to provide evidence based comparative data on the effectiveness

and efficiency of the investment in such preventive and management empowerment programmes in specific populations.

5. To elaborate policy recommendations and specific guidelines to contribute to the scaling up of the stratification and CDSMP adaptation in other regions and countries in Europe.

6. To exploit and disseminate all the achievements of EFFICHRONIC to contribute to reduce the burden of chronic conditions in Europe.

Developing effective strategies to reach out the identified vulnerable individuals and groups (objective 2) is certainly key to the success of the project. Those identified individuals will be recruited to receive chronic disease self-management training through the participation in the CDSMP. To this end, EFFICHRONIC will identify and learn from successful and innovative experiences of sampling, recruiting vulnerable populations in health-related interventions around Europe and worldwide, and will adapt the insights and methodologies to the specific goals and different contexts of the project.

As part of the overall communication strategy of EFFICHRONIC, different workshops and events have been planned. These aim at engaging with public health and chronic care experts, professionals and decision-makers. The first workshop seeks to present EFFICHRONIC goals, frameworks and methodologies to a wide community of people in each national setting, to consider different strategies for reaching out vulnerable populations, and to discuss and co-produce an evaluation framework to assess the efficiency and cost-benefit of the chronic care interventions that promote patient empowerment, with a special focus on the social determinants of health.

2. Background paper: purpose and scope

The current background paper has been produced with the goal of encouraging and supporting professionals, experts and decision-makers' discussions to develop effective strategies to reach out the identified vulnerable individuals and groups (objective 2). Workshops to facilitate discussions will be held in each of the countries of the participating members of the EFFICHRONIC consortium during the initial phase of the project.

This paper is therefore a work-in-progress document that is initially provided as discussion guide for the workshops, which will benefit from the workshop debates, and which will be later enriched from the expert contributions and suggestions. The audience may suggest successful interventions or best practices that the EFFICHRONIC team will further investigate and incorporate into the design of the project.

This paper starts with a brief conceptual discussion on the term “vulnerable” populations and its related terms and reflects on the reasons why these populations are hard-to-reach for health interventions (with a particular focus on chronic care interventions). Then, a section which identifies and suggests a number of experiences for sampling, recruiting and retaining vulnerable people in health interventions is followed.

3. Terminology

EFFICHRONIC aims at implementing CDSMP in those groups of society mostly exposed to the negative effect of the conditions in which they are born, grow, live, work and age, i.e., the social determinants of health, responsible for the unfair and avoidable differences in the health status. These groups will be referred as “vulnerable” during the project EFFICHRONIC.

- **Vulnerable groups**

The concept of vulnerability is more intuitive than analytical, and the broad social science literature uses this term with a broad meaning. In EFFICHRONIC we will adopt the definition used by international organisations such as the World Health Organisation⁵ and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies⁶. These define vulnerability as “ the diminished capacity of an individual or group to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from the impact of a natural or man-made hazard”.

A common use of the term vulnerability refers to people in poverty or marginalised. Vulnerable people would equate to “poor”, “marginalised”, “deprived” or “disadvantaged”

⁵ http://www.who.int/environmental_health_emergencies/vulnerable_groups/en/

⁶ See <http://www.ifrc.org/en/what-we-do/disaster-management/about-disasters/what-is-a-disaster/what-is-vulnerability/>

and would typically include: homeless⁷ people; sex workers; drug users; people living with HIV; people from sexual minority communities; asylum seekers, refugees (also called displaced migrants); people from ethnic minority communities (cultural and linguistic minorities); traveller families (including Roma people); prisoners; etc. (Department of Health 2002; Flanagan and Hancock 2010). However, vulnerability can equally appear even if the individual has his/her basic needs (food, housing, etc.) covered but the individual lacks instead family or social ties. “Vulnerability is most often associated with poverty, but it can also arise when people are isolated, insecure and defenceless in the face of risk, shock or stress”⁸.

In a 2006 report by the Spanish Red Cross, vulnerability is defined as an “intermediate zone” in which everybody can enter at certain moments in life and due to quite different reasons (a catastrophic or life changing event can render everybody vulnerable). “The zone of social vulnerability is located between the zone of social integration (a stable job, solid social and family pillars) and the zone of social exclusion (jobless, social isolation, lack of family ties), thus becoming a more unstable zone, with precarious jobs, intermittent periods of employment and unemployment and with weak social and family relations” (Cruz Roja 2006)”. Thus, the Red Cross report captured key profiles of individuals in a situation of vulnerability, led by “young foreigner homeless” and “Spanish homeless” and followed by “young and qualified foreigner women without income”, “young and qualified foreigner women with family problems” and “Spanish pensioner women”⁹.

In line with the above, we suggest distinguishing two broad dimensions of the concept: an “individual” dimension and a “social” dimension.

⁷ The term “homeless” is contested, perceived and tackled differently according to the country. EFFICHRONIC suggests the broad definition of homelessness of the European Typology of Homelessness and Housing Exclusion (ETHOS) developed by the Fédération Européenne d’Associations Nationales Travaillant avec les Sans-Abri AISBL (FEANTSA) (European Federation of National Associations Working with the Homeless). According to this definition, homeless are not only people who are roofless, but also people who are houseless and people who live in temporary, insecure and inadequate poor quality housing. So, homeless can comprise.

- rooflessness (without a shelter of any kind, sleeping rough)
- houselessness (with a place to sleep but temporary in institutions or shelter)
- living in insecure housing (threatened with severe exclusion due to insecure tenancies, eviction, domestic violence)
- living in inadequate housing (in caravans on illegal campsites, in unfit housing, in extreme overcrowding).

⁸ See <http://www.ifrc.org/en/what-we-do/disaster-management/about-disasters/what-is-a-disaster/what-is-vulnerability/>

⁹ Red Cross Spain regularly produces a Vulnerability report: the latest published has been the Informe sobre la Vulnerabilidad Social 2014 <http://www.cruzroja.es/principal/documents/449219/451193/IVS+2014+vs+interactiva.pdf/71b3cd58-9cd5-43fe-a75e-c3ed4b0b5006>

- a) **The individual dimension** looks at physical and psychological aspects of the individual which lead to a situation of vulnerability. The chronically ill, disabled, frail elderly or people suffering from mental health problems can be under severe stress and hence be in a situation of vulnerability.
- b) **The social dimension** of the concept perceives vulnerability by considering societal factors and the environments where people live in and which derived from the social and economic structures. Thus, vulnerable people are those socioeconomically disadvantaged, excluded from participating fully in society or suffering from stigma and discrimination, violence and abuse or restrictions in exercising civil and political rights.

The EFFICHRONIC project will use the term “vulnerable” as an umbrella concept which includes people suffering from social exclusion and socio-economic hardship, as well as people under stress for physical or psychological reasons. The following graph aims to capture the analytical approach to vulnerability that will be adopted by the EFFICHRONIC project.

- **Hard-to-reach**

A related concept for the EFFICHRONIC project is that these vulnerable groups are usually “hard-to-reach”. Flanagan and Hancock (2010) suggest the reasons why these groups may be not accessible for the health services: (i) because these people lack choice to attend; (ii) because of stigma; (iii) because services themselves create barriers that impede people coming through our doors; (iv) because they have fallen through the care net (people let down by the system); etc.

Eventually, reaching vulnerable people may be also difficult because they may not associate with other members. Populations with a high proportion of non-associative members are “defined by individual attributes such as physiological or health status. There is not often an overriding reason for population not socializing and a substantial proportion of population not having strong social links with other members and, indeed, many might even resist such contact (Thompson and Philips, 2007: 1292). Reaching to “non-associative” individuals (i.e., people with mental health problems; old people living alone) may entail different recruiting strategies than identifiable groups of vulnerable people (i.e. Roma people, travellers, asylum seekers).

The EFFICHRONIC project focuses on those vulnerable people who are non-users of health care services (“they don’t come to see us”; “they would not seek support from the usual avenues”) (Flanagan and Hancock, 2010). Hence, they are “hard-to-reach” for the health services and have traditionally been “underserved”.

- **Are all vulnerable people candidates for CDSMP training?**

The CDSMP methodology requires certain basic levels of intellectual capacity, mobility, and ability to make personal choices and certain stability in one’s life project without which it becomes extremely difficult to fully participate and benefit from the programme. For example, people sleeping on the street every night (“roofless people”) might find very hard to engage with the basics of the CDSMP, including regularly attending a weekly two-and-a-half hours workshop for six consecutive weeks or making use of the

educational material provided with the training course. However, people sleeping in temporary accommodation or shelters or living in supported shared flats with other housemates might be candidates to join the CDSMP. Likewise, people with severe mental health problems might be unable to even sit in a 10-16 people meeting and actively take part in the workshop; but people with minor mental health conditions might be totally suitable to join this type of programmes.

Another key element to apply the CDSMP training is the participation of Leaders. These are usually (although not exclusively) non-professionals (peers) with one or more chronic conditions who voluntarily facilitate the workshop using a detailed, scripted manual (Stanford 2016). Hence, identifying, recruiting and managing suitable Leaders from certain vulnerable groups should be a matter of concern and requires careful thinking.

EFFICHRONIC will establish two age threshold across the board: participants must be between 18 and 80 year-old. Beyond this, EFFICHRONIC needs to explore the establishment of other thresholds which might however vary according to the vulnerable groups or individuals considered.. The Stanford Administration/Implementation Manual (Stanford 2016) does not provide much guidance on these points. This document compiles examples to point specific elements to consider which do not aim to predetermine the discussion of the workshops.

a) Vulnerable individuals due to physical and psychological aspects (such as fragile old people, with certain disabilities or with mental health problems) may not participate due to mobility issues, learning difficulties, etc. Thus, EFFICHRONIC might consider whether to target elderly people participation to those (i) able to come to the workshop, (ii) able to stay for the 2 and a half hours that the workshop lasts; and (iii) with sufficient cognitive ability as to understand the logic, purpose and dynamics of the training.

b) Vulnerable individuals and groups due to their socio-economic status or social exclusion situation might be subject to other limitations. As mentioned above, people sleeping on the street every night might not be suitable to join EFFICHRONIC. In the case of migrants and foreign people, a good command of Spanish is needed.

Workshop. Exercise 1

- EFFICHRONIC is considering prioritizing the intervention with the following vulnerable individuals/groups:
 - a) Due to physical and psychological aspects:
 - The frail elderly
 - The disabled
 - b) Due to their socio-economic status or social exclusion
 - (Legal) migrants
 - Living on benefits
 - Prisoners

- Using Table 1, discuss which vulnerable populations should be considered for the implementation of the EFFICHRONIC project. Describe why each of these selected populations may be hard-to-reach in Asturias.

Table 1. Characteristics of the vulnerable populations to work with.

Group	Characteristics of the group: What do members have in common?	Do they get together? Where?	How many are there in the group?	Which organizations work with this group?	Are there individuals we could work with them?	Which characteristics render them unsuitable for CDSMP?

4. Strategies for Sampling and Recruiting in the CDSMP

CDSMP has been applied to low income, urban or rural people and people from minority populations (Hispanic) of North America and elsewhere¹⁰. The strategies for sampling and recruiting vulnerable populations tend to be limited to advertising the CDSMP courses on the local media, on community organisations bulletins and at health centres. The CDSMP Administration/Implementation Manual (Stanford 2016) mentions the local media (radio, TV), church bulletins, school newsletters, social clubs, etc. It also suggests the use of electronic media. However, the common hard-to-reach characteristic of the individuals and groups that are the target of the EFFICHRONIC project poses challenges that are not directly addressed by the Stanford Administration/Implementation Manual (Stanford 2016). How to identify hard-to-reach (or even “hidden”) vulnerable populations with chronic conditions that might be candidates to the CDSMP?

5. Strategies for sampling and recruiting vulnerable individuals due to their physical and psychological conditions

As mentioned above, individuals and groups typically considered within this dimension include the frail elderly living alone, people with health conditions or life limiting illnesses (congenital abnormalities, genetic conditions, hearing loss, mental health problems). The identifying element of these people is not the lack of basic resources, and hence, they are not necessarily receiving social services support or included in any social care registry. They live in their own house and have sufficient resources to live and support themselves. They seek care from their primary care centre and, if their health situation worsens, they may be taken to hospital – but their own home is their usual place of living. How could EFFICHRONIC get to them?

5.1. Sampling and recruiting at health organizations

¹⁰ For example, to low-income urban residents in Anchorage (Alaska) (Alaska Section, 2013)

As mentioned above, elderly people or people with mental health problems seek regular care from their primary care or mental health centre and, if their health situation worsens, they may be taken to hospital. Thus, all these health care sites can be places to identify and recruit them. EFFICHRONIC may consider recruiting individuals through GP practices, at the hospital wards or at the A&E door.

Recruiting at an Urban Community Health Center in Alaska (Alaska Section, 2013).

In order to be qualified as a workshop participant in this study, the individual had to attend 1 or more sessions of a CDSMP or diabetes training workshop between April and October 2009. Self-management training was widely advertised at the clinics and patients with diabetes were actively recruited. The control group was selected from the Community Health Center registry of patients with diabetes who did not attend any self-management training beyond usual care

Targeting frequent users of Primary Health Care services (Hudon et al. 2016)

This study aimed to examine factors associated with acceptance and completion rates of the CDSMP among frequent users of health care services. It was conducted in 4 family medicine groups, including 38 practices, in the Saguenay-Lac-Saint-Jean region of the Province of Quebec (Canada). Patients had to be aged between 18 and 80 years, with at least one chronic disease (diabetes, cardiovascular, respiratory or musculoskeletal disease or chronic pain) and targeted by their family physician as a frequent user of health care services who would benefit from participating in a case management intervention by a primary care nurse (10). The family physicians received a list of their frequent users (who consulted the Emergency Department and/or were hospitalized three or more times in the previous year). The CDSMP was explained and offered to each patient by his or her case management nurse. Groups included patients with different chronic diseases. In total, 167 frequent users of services were recruited for case management and were also invited to participate in the CDSMP. 60 patients out of the 167 accepted the participation in the programme.

5.2. Sampling and Recruiting at the neighbourhood

Where do all elderly people living alone necessarily go to meet their basic needs?.

6. Strategies for sampling and recruiting vulnerable individuals and groups due to their socio-economic status or social exclusion situation.

We may want to borrow from the literature on researching on hidden and hard-to-reach socially disadvantaged groups. This literature suggests non-probability sampling techniques, including snowballing through social networks; venue-based time-location; respondent-driven sampling; targeted sampling; capture-recapture; adaptive sampling; sampling through community organizations; etc. (Bonevski et al. 2014). In here, only a number of these techniques will be discussed.

Before moving to the analysis of specific sampling and recruiting techniques, it is worth mentioning that the literature recognises the importance of tailoring recruitment methods to the culture of the target population if this is from an specific ethnic minority (Burns et al. 2008). These methods include: the use of posters and flyers illustrated with ethnic minority individuals (i.e. African Americans) posted in doctors' offices, clinics, churches, hairdressers, and barbershops; hiring people from the community to recruit by making presentations at churches, community centers, health fairs, or event; making telephone calls to potential participants; etc.

6.1. Sampling and Recruiting at health care organizations

Homeless people attending hospital A&E

Hewett N et al. (2016) Clin Med (Lond) Randomised controlled trial of GP-led in-hospital management of homeless people ('Pathway'), 16 (3): 223-9.

Homeless people have complex problems. GP enhanced care (Pathway) has shown benefits. We performed a randomised, -parallel arm trial at two large inner city hospitals. Inpatient homeless adults were randomly allocated to either standard care (all management by the hospital-based clinical team) or enhanced care with input from a homeless care team. The hospital data system provided healthcare usage information, and we used questionnaires to assess quality of life. 206 patients were allocated to enhanced care and 204 to usual care. Length of stay (up to 90 days after admission) did not differ between groups (standard care 14.0 days, enhanced care 13.3 days). Average reattendance at the emergency department within a year was 5.8 visits in the standard

care group and 4.8 visits with enhanced care, but this decrease was not significant. - Quality of life scores after discharge (in 108 patients) improved with enhanced care (EQ-5D-5L score increased by 0.12 [95% CI 0.032 to 0.22] compared with 0.03 [-0.1 to 0.15; $p=0.076$] with standard care). The proportion of people sleeping on the streets after discharge was 14.6% in the standard care arm and 3.8% in the enhanced care arm ($p=0.034$). The quality-of-life cost per quality-adjusted life-year was £26,000. The Pathway approach doesn't alter length of stay but improves quality of life and reduces street-homelessness.

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27251910>

6.2. Sampling and recruiting through community organisations

Voluntary and Community sector organisations (Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charity and religious groups, etc.) who work with vulnerable populations can be a useful partner in identifying individuals, families and groups. Community organisations' registries of the people they are providing support – such as the Caritas registry described below- can be a useful sampling tool. Community organisations' volunteers could be really helpful in recruiting and incorporating potential participants into EFFICHRONIC.

Using the Caritas registry to identify homeless individuals or families

Ana M. Novoa, Davide Malmusi, Julia Ward, Fernando Díaz, Jordi Bosch, Mercè Darnell, Carme Trilla, Carme Borrell (2014) Living and housing conditions and health status among people attended by Caritas Barcelona and living in substandard housing. Brussels: European Network of Homeless Health Workers (ENHW-FEANTSA)

<http://www.feantsa.org/en/newsletter/2015/01/14/european-network-of-homeless-health-workers-issue-20?bcParent=27>

Report describing the socio-demographic characteristics, housing conditions and health status of these families before undergoing rehousing. The study population was obtained from the Caritas registry: several families (or single persons) living in substandard dwelling conditions (inadequate housing habitability conditions or overcrowding) as assessed by Caritas' social workers from the Direct Attention Service (DAS), were identified and invited to participate in the study. Those who agreed to participate were interviewed face-to-face by a trained interviewer at the Caritas' centre in Barcelona between September and December 2012 ($n=175$). Also, 145 additional Caritas users

with difficulties paying housing costs (rent or mortgage) and having been attended by Caritas's Housing Mediation Service (HMS) were also interviewed.

*This study is part of the SOPHIE research, project funded from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme. It aims to generate new evidence on the impact of structural policies on health inequalities, and to develop innovative methodologies for the evaluation of these policies in Europe. <http://www.sophie-project.eu/index.htm>

Diabetes prevention and diagnosis: reaching out to vulnerable groups in Portugal

The Portuguese Diabetes Association – APDP has been partnering with the Ernest Roma Foundation since 2009 to carry out a series of projects aiming to promote diabetes prevention, early diagnosis and proper diabetes management for the poorest and most marginalised. Initiatives include large screening and diagnosis campaigns, as well as educational workshops in more disadvantaged neighbourhoods and training courses for social workers and other personal care assistants.

The joint initiative has been far-reaching, with currently more than 11,000 people screened. Coordinated under the auspices of the Portuguese Programme for Diabetes, the project is one of the major initiatives to promote healthier lifestyles amongst the poorest and most marginalised populations who are struggling with access to healthcare, information and training and therefore have a higher risk of developing diabetes. See www.apdp.pt or www.fundacaoernestoroma.org

Alternative registries or sources of information on people in need might be held by other social organizations, such as the Red Cross or *Fédération Européenne d'Associations Nationales Travaillant avec les Sans-Abri AISBL* (FEANTSA). In Asturias, the Albergue Covadonga y la Asociación Albéniz, through Faciam (<http://faciam.org/faciam/>) are FEANTSA members.

6.3. Venue based time-location

Venue based time-location has been widely used for conducting research and developing interventions with hard-to-reach groups such as men who have sex with

men, homeless people or drug users. The key principle is that these populations are approached in those places and at those times when they tend to meet up and gather. For example, homeless people may be approached at a charity association at the time meals are served.

The Homeless People Survey (Encuesta a Personas sin Hogar-2012) is a Spain-wide survey conducted with homeless individuals who attend social accommodation and/or feeding services in towns bigger than 20.000 population. The survey was conducted between the 13th February and the 25th March, as that is the period when demand for sleeping and meals is higher.

*In Asturias, 6 centres (3 providing accommodation; 3 providing meals) participated in the EPSH-2012

<http://www.ine.es/prensa/np761.pdf>

The methodology is quite sophisticated though and includes three basic components: formative research to learn the venues, times, and methods to recruit the people; monthly sampling frames of eligible venues and day-time periods that met attendance, logistical, and safety criteria; and recruitment of participants in accordance with randomly generated venue calendars (MacKellar et al. 2007).

6.4. Respondent-driven sampling

Respondent-driven sampling (RDS) is a technique in which participants recruit one another, similar to snowball sampling. It is particularly used with “hidden” populations such as injection drug users, men who have sex with men, and commercial sex workers. Typically, other standard sampling methods (including targeted sampling and time-location sampling) reveal less useful to engage with these populations (Goel and Salganik 2010). The process starts by “selecting a small number of initial participants (“seeds”) from the target population who are asked—and typically provided financial incentive—to recruit their contacts in the population. The sampling proceeds with current sample members recruiting the next wave of sample members, continuing until the desired sample size is reached. Participants are usually allowed to recruit up to three other contacts in order to ensure sampling continues even if some sample members do not recruit” (Goel and Salganik 2010).

6.5. Combinations of recruitment strategies

Combination of recruitment strategies

Horowitz CR et al. (2009) Effective Recruitment of Minority Populations through Community-Led Strategies, *Am J Prev Med.* 37 (6 Suppl 1): 195–200.

Background—Community-based participatory research (CBPR) may be an important strategy for partnering with and reaching populations who bear a greater burden of illness but have been historically difficult to engage. A Community Action Board of 20 East Harlem (Manhattan, USA) residents, leaders and advocates used CBPR to compare the effectiveness of different strategies in recruiting and enrolling adults with pre-diabetes into a peer-led diabetes prevention intervention.

Methods—The Board created 5 different recruitment strategies:

- recruiting through clinicians: educating local clinicians about pre-diabetes, giving them a toolkit and referral cards so clinicians could easily refer patients. Followed up with all clinicians through phone calls, visits and educational sessions.
- at large public events like health fairs, street fairs and farmer's markets. Partners set up tables with banners, giveaways and community members, who were greeters, encouraged their neighbours to learn.
- organizing special local recruitment events, such as Stop Diabetes Day (advertised in local newspapers, flyers, e-mail blasts and at local businesses and housing developments. These included live music, dancing, healthy foods and giveaways specifically tailored to identifying potential enrollees).
- recruiting at local organizations and garnering their support in approaching their clients about the study.
- a partner-led approach in which community partners developed and managed the recruitment efforts at their sites. Community advocates spearheaded these efforts and voiced their needs to make recruitment work at their organizations. They explained and championed the study to their own constituents and invited researchers into the process once people understood the study and showed interest in taking part. In this process, they also told the research staff what would be needed

to make recruitment work, including appropriate timing of events, staffing, refreshments, incentives, and taught research staff how to interact with clients.

Study personnel were trained to collect data about the number of people approached through each strategy, the number who consented and returned for pre-diabetes testing, and the number who had pre-diabetes and were enrolled in the trial. Each person would report to a welcome desk, where Partners or staff captured the data on the number of people who were approached and who declined further participation before they could be screened for eligibility. At that point, staff used a computerized data management system to collect data on the flow of each person through the study. All people approached for the study received a gift after this information was obtained. The study analyst used chi-square statistics to determine the most effective enrolment strategy and differences between those enrolled and the overall East Harlem population.

Results—In 3 months, 555 local adults were approached; 249 were appropriate candidates for further evaluation (overweight, non-pregnant, East Harlem residents without known diabetes); 179 consented and returned fasting for 1/2 day of pre-diabetes testing; and 99 had pre-diabetes and enrolled in a pilot randomized trial. The partner-led approach was most successful, recruiting 68% of people enrolled. This was also the most efficient strategy; 34% of those approached through partners were ultimately enrolled, versus 0%–17% through the other four strategies. Participants were predominantly low-income, uninsured, undereducated Spanish-speaking women.

Workshop Exercise 3

- Using Table 3 below, discuss potential sampling and recruiting strategies for the vulnerable individuals due to their socio-economic status or social exclusion situation

Group	What can be done?	Which resources should we deploy?	Which limitations may exist?	Any other examples to get learn from?

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ANNEX 3: APPROVAL OF THE QUALITATIVE STUDY BY THE ETHICS COMMITTEE

Oviedo, 11 de Abril de 2019

El Comité de Ética de la Investigación con Medicamentos del Principado de Asturias, ha revisado el Proyecto de Investigación nº 118/19, titulado: "EVALUACION CUALITATIVA DE LOS PROCESOS DE CAPTACIÓN Y RECLUTAMIENTO EN EL PROYECTO EFFICHRONIC". Investigadora Principal, Dña. Marta Pisano González, Servicio de Promoción de la Salud. Dirección General de Salud Pública.

Prolongación/Evaluación reclutamiento Estudio previo 20/17 (***"Análisis de la eficiencia de un programa de autogestión de la enfermedad crónica en población con vulnerabilidad socio-económica"***). Investigadora principal: Marta Pisano).

El Comité ha tomado el acuerdo de considerar que el citado proyecto reúne las condiciones éticas necesarias para poder realizarse y en consecuencia emite su autorización.

Los Consentimientos informados deberán firmarse por duplicado (para dejar constancia de ello) y una copia deberá ser archivada con la documentación del estudio.

Le recuerdo que deberá guardarse la máxima confidencialidad de los datos utilizados en este proyecto.

Fdo: Mauricio Telenti Asensio
Secretario del Comité de Ética de la Investigación
del Principado de Asturias

